

جامعة الإسكندرية
ALEXANDRIA
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Alexandria University
Medical Research Institute

**Medical Research Institute
Department of Biomedical Informatics and Medical Statistics**

**Obese patient preference regarding bariatric surgery:
An adaptive choice based conjoint analysis.**

**A Thesis Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements
For the degree of Master of Science**

In

Biomedical Informatics and Medical Statistics

Submitted by

Doaa Hussein Hassan Dewedar

B. Sc. of Pharmacy, Faculty of Pharmacy and Drug Manufacturing
Pharos University, 2019

2023

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Approval sheet

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that no part of this dissertation has been submitted to Alexandria University or any other university in Egypt or abroad as a part of the requirements to obtain another degree. Alexandria University's code of ethics and rules of academic integrity have been followed.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AA	:	African American
ACBC	:	Adaptive choice based conjoint analysis
AGB	:	Adjustable gastric banding
AGB	:	Adjustable gastric band
AGB	:	Adjustable gastric banding
BMI	:	Body mass index
BPD	:	Biliopancreatic diversion
BYO	:	Build Your Own
CA	:	Conjoint analysis
CAD	:	Coronary artery disease
CBC	:	Standard choice based conjoint analysis
CCEA	:	Convergent Cluster & Ensemble Analysis
CDC	:	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
CVDs	:	Cardiovascular diseases
DALYs	:	Disutility adjusted life years
DCE	:	Discrete choice experiment
DS	:	Duodenal switch
GB	:	Gastric bypass
GERD	:	Gastroesophageal reflux disease
GP	:	Gastric plication
HB	:	Hierarchical Bayes
HF	:	Heart failure
IARC	:	International Agency for Research on Cancer
IBD	:	Inflammatory bowel disease
ICER	:	Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio
IFSO	:	International Federation for the Surgery of Obesity and Metabolic Disorders
ISPOR	:	International Society for Pharmacoeconomics and Outcomes Research
LAGB	:	Laparoscopic adjustable gastric banding
LRYGB	:	Laparoscopic Roux-en-Y gastric bypass
LSG	:	Laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy
LSG	:	Laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy

NCDs	:	Noncommunicable diseases
NHANES	:	National Health and Nutrition Examination
NHS	:	National Health Service
NICE	:	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence
QALYs	:	Quality adjusted life years
QoL	:	Quality of Life
RYGB	:	Roux-en-Y gastric bypass
SG	:	Sleeve gastrectomy
SO	:	Sarcopenic obesity
WCSS	:	Within-cluster sum of squares
WHO	:	World Health Organization
WTP	:	Willingness to pay

ABSTRACT

Objective: Measure obese patient's preferences for the risks, benefits, and other attributes of bariatric surgery in a group of patients who are candidates for bariatric surgery in Alexandria. Setting: The bariatric surgery clinic of the Medical Research Institute, Alexandria University. Method: An Adaptive choice based conjoint analysis experiment of measuring the obese patient's preference for bariatric surgery. Each surgical profile was described by the following attributes: (1) treatment method, (2) recovery and reversibility, (3) years treatment has been available, (4) expected weight loss, (5) effect on other medical conditions, (6) risk of complication, (7) side effects, (8) changes to diet, (9) out-of-pocket costs. Participants conducted 4 sections online survey: (1) sociodemographic characteristics, (2) BYO (Build Your Own) section, (3) screening section, and (4) choice tournament section. A convenience sample of patients seeking weight loss was recruited from the bariatric surgery clinic of the Medical Research Institute, Alexandria University.

Results: Among the 299 respondents (75.6% women; 56.9% aged between 30 and 44 years), surgical profiles of hypothetical procedures that included higher weight loss (coefficient for loss of 80% of excess weight and regain 0%, 28.04 [95%CI, 23.07, to 33.01]), lower risk of complications (coefficient for 0% risk of complication, 34.26 [95%CI, 27.96 to 40.57]), and lower adverse effects (coefficient for no adverse effects, 21.63 [95%CI, 15.75 to 27.51]) were most likely to be selected. K-mean cluster analysis identified the following 2 subgroups: risk tacker group more concerned on excess weight loss (coefficient value for loss of 80% of excess weight and regain 0%, 29.04 [95% CI, 21.38 to 36.71], surgery availability(coefficient value for 10 year availability, 14.59 [95% CI, 7.46 to 21.71] and diet change(coefficient value for normal food with a small portion and buy vitamins, 34.94 [95% CI, 29.79 to 40.09] and risk averse group more concerned on the risk of complication(0% risk of complications, 62.98[95% CI, 52.74 to 73.22], adverse effect(coefficient value for "No adverse effect", 45.80 [95% CI, 37.7 to 53.91], and surgery mechanism of action(coefficient value for restrict food and decrease hunger, 34.35 [95% CI, 29.49 to 39.21]).

Conclusions: Candidates for bariatric surgery consider weight loss without regaining followed by risk of complication within 3 years and adverse effects as the most important attributes, while the least important attributes are initial out of pocket and resolving of medical condition.

1. INTRODUCTION

Obesity is a chronic, relapsing, multifactorial, neurobehavioral disease, where an increase in body fat promotes adipose tissue dysfunction and results in adverse metabolic, biomechanical, and psychosocial health consequences (Bray, 2004).

The WHO defines obesity as abnormal or excessive fat accumulation that may impair health (World Health Organization [WHO], 2021).

Current guidelines from the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) and the WHO define the normal adult's BMI range as 18.5 to 24.9 kg/m², whereas a BMI ≥ 25 kg/m² is considered to be overweight, ≥ 30 kg/m² as obese, and ≥ 40 kg/m² as severely obese (WHO, 2015).

Obesity is the fourth most common risk factor for many noncommunicable diseases (NCDs) after high blood pressure, dietary risks, and tobacco, affecting almost 60% of adults, 29% of boys, and 27% of girls in the European Region. It was also the leading risk factor for disability, causing 7% of total years lived with disability, and recently was linked to greater morbidity and mortality from COVID-19 (WHO, 2022).

The disease impacts most body systems. It affects the heart, liver, kidneys, joints, and reproductive system. It leads to a range of non-communicable diseases (NCDs), such as type 2 diabetes, cardiovascular disease, hypertension and stroke, and various forms of cancer, as well as mental health issues. Recently, it was found that obese are also three times more likely to be hospitalized for COVID-19 (WHO, 2022).

In the UK, national cohort research showed that every 5 kg/m² rise in BMI beyond 25 kg/m² resulted in a hazard ratio of 1.21 (1.20–1.22) for all-cause mortality, 1.29 (1.27–1.30) for cardiovascular mortality, and 1.13 (1.12–1.14) for cancer mortality (Bhaskaran et al., 2018). Overweight and obesity were linked to roughly 4 million deaths and 120 million disability-adjusted life years globally in 2015, according to a comprehensive examination of the health impacts of high BMI using Global Burden of Disease research data and methodology in 195 countries between 1990 and 2015. More than two-thirds of fatalities associated with obesity were caused by cardiovascular disease (Afshin et al., 2017).

Obesity accounted for 4.7 million premature deaths in 2017, according to the Global Burden of Disease research. To put this in context, this was nearly four times the number of people killed in car accidents and nearly five times the number of people killed by HIV/AIDS in 2017 (Ritchie & Roser, 2017).

In Egypt, obesity is expected to cause around 115 thousand deaths (19.08 % of total estimated deaths in 2020), also disability adjusted life years (DALYs) related to obesity may have reached 4 million (Aboulghate et al., 2021).

1.1 Causes of obesity

Numerous elements including environmental, genetic, and behavioral variables, contribute to the development of obesity (Panuganti & Lenehan, 2017). In addition, the gut microbiome which consists of several types of microbes including bacteria, archaea, eukaryotes, viruses, and parasites (Lozupone et al., 2012) has recently been identified as a significant contributor to the etiology of obesity (Duranti et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2017). According to experts, the primary factor of being overweight is the absence of an energy balance, which is established by matching the energy ingested through meals to the amount spent in daily activities (Mohammed et al., 2018).

1.2 Obesity prevalence

Obesity is the most common nutritional disease in the United States, affecting about 36% of adults (WHO, 2021). The global prevalence of overweight and obesity has doubled since 1980, with nearly one-third of the world's population being categorized as overweight or obese (Global Burden of Disease Collaborative Network [GBD], 2017). The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC] (2014) response to the obesity epidemic began in 1999, based on the results of its annual population health surveys, one of these surveys is the National Health and Nutrition Examination (NHANES).

In 2022 more than 1 billion people worldwide were obese about 650 million adults, 340 million adolescents, and 39 million children. This number is expected to increase further. According to WHO estimates, 167 million adults and children will suffer from a deterioration in their health by 2025, due to obesity or overweight (WHO, 2022).

In the Eastern Mediterranean Region, the prevalence of obesity increased for adults from 15.1 % in 1980 to 20.7 % in 2015. It also increased for children from 4.1 % to 4.9 % during the same period (GBD 2015 Eastern Mediterranean Region Obesity Collaborators, 2018).

1.3 Prevalence of obesity in Egypt

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), regarding obesity, Egypt is ranked the 18th country in the world (Encyclopaedia Britannica, 2020). Egypt had the greatest level of age-standardized adult obesity (35.3%) (Afshin et al., 2017).

1.4 Obesity complication and health burden

Obesity is linked to several comorbid conditions, such as diabetes, heart disease, obstructive sleep apnea, and cancer; nevertheless, modest weight loss of at least 5% to 10% can considerably improve health-related problems (Fruh, 2017). Having a large waistline may affect endocrine and immune system functions (Hua et al., 2022). The "obesity paradox" has been found in patients with pneumonia and sepsis, when excess weight inhibits immune responses and enhances infection susceptibility (Nie et al., 2014). Moreover, Obesity was also recognized as a key factor in the onset and progression of renal disease. A condition is defined as "obesity-related nephropathy"(Lu et al., 2015). Furthermore, Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) including coronary artery disease, stroke, and heart failure, are a collection of serious consequences of obesity and continue to be the leading cause of death in Western nations (Koliaki et al., 2019).

The risk of cardiovascular disease is higher in obese people. The most common side effect of obesity on the cardiovascular system is atrial fibrillation, which should be considered if pulmonary hypertension is present. Other cardiovascular pathology related to fat accumulation are increased blood volume and cardiac output, secondary ventricular hypertrophy, and diastolic dysfunction (Schetz et al., 2019). Obesity directly influences changes in hematologic markers and thrombosis risk (Purdy & Shatzel, 2021).

The International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) Working Group claims that obesity is causally linked to a higher risk of developing a variety of malignancies. Such adult cancers associated with obesity include esophageal adenocarcinoma, colorectal, renal, pancreatic, liver, and gallbladder cancer. Obesity's exact contribution to the genesis and progression of cancer has not yet been completely understood. Changes in adipokines, steroid hormone production, insulin/insulin-like growth factor signaling, the cancer microenvironment, and a low level of chronic inflammation may be key factors explaining the relationship between obesity and cancer (Hopkins et al., 2016; Iyengar et al., 2016).

Furthermore, obese women with breast cancer have a higher chance of local recurrence than women who are of normal weight besides more obstacles in patient care and disease management since the effectiveness of cancer therapies is much poorer in this special patient population. Therefore, they could encounter greater radiation and surgical-related difficulties, suffering from decreased effectiveness of endocrine therapy. Also, systemic chemotherapy seems to work less well in this case (Lee et al., 2019). Multiple obesity-related comorbidities are caused by systemic, interactive disturbances to human organs, which eventually increase the chance of mortality.

1.5 Economic burden of obesity

In all nations, regardless of location or financial level, obesity has a significant economic impact. For eight nations (Saudi Arabia, Spain, India, South Africa, Brazil, Thailand, Mexico, and Australia) from 2019 to 2060, the direct and indirect costs of obesity were calculated using a cost-of-illness economic evaluation technique. It was determined that maintaining obesity prevalence at 2019 levels or decreasing it by 5% from anticipated levels would result in an average yearly decrease in economic costs of 5.2 and 13.2 %, respectively (Okunogbe et al., 2021). Additionally, obesity raises the likelihood of unemployment and lowers payment (Goettler et al., 2017). Egypt's economy suffers 62 billion Egyptian pounds annually on treating complications related to obesity (Aboulghate et al., 2021).

1.6 Treatment modules of obesity

There are three main weight-control interventions: diet and exercise intervention, medication therapy, and bariatric surgery.

1.6.1 Diet and exercise

All recommendations encourage food modification and increased physical activity as the first line of treatment for those who are overweight or obese (Ritten & LaManna, 2017). Resistance exercise improves body composition and physical performance in persons with sarcopenic obesity (SO), which is a term used to characterize the syndrome involving both low muscle mass (sarcopenia) and excessive body fat (obesity) (Batsis & Villareal, 2018).

It should also be highlighted that a crucial part of weight-loss regimens is dietary education (Novais et al., 2019). Numerous dietary regimens have been offered over the years, but none of them are both effective and safe for every patient. As a result, the patient's demands, routines, and clinical state should be taken into account while developing the patient's treatment regimen (Johnston et al., 2014).

The long-term effectiveness of dietary therapy is, however, adversely affected by the frequent issue of weight regain. Furthermore, current research shows that the amount of weight gained back after the dietary intervention doesn't depend on the rate of weight loss (Coutinho et al., 2018).

1.6.2 Medications

Currently, the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) recommends pharmacological therapy in addition to a low-calorie diet and the appropriate exercise routine for weight reduction maintenance. Orlistat, phentermine, diethylpropion, benzphetamine, phendimetrazine, lorcaserin liraglutide, and naltrexone with bupropion are well-known medications that have received approval from the US Food and Drug Administration for the treatment of obesity (U.S. Food and Drug Administration [FDA], 2015).

The ability to adopt combination treatments, which may improve the efficacy of single therapy and might mimic the various mechanisms that contribute to the advantages of bariatric surgery, arising from the diversity of appetite control systems (Camilleri & Acosta, 2018).

Greater weight reduction (mean 11.3 kg) was seen with Endobarrier which is a gastrointestinal liner, a non-surgical medical device for the treatment of type 2 diabetes and obesity when used plus liraglutide treatment as compared to liraglutide treatment alone (mean 4.5 kg) (Sen Gupta et al., 2016).

Recently, the National Health Service (NHS) has a very small number of pharmacological alternatives, the majority of which are only approved for the maintenance of weight reduction in patients with a BMI of >27 kg/m² with associated risk factors or BMI ≥ 30 kg/m². Nevertheless, if less than 5% of the target weight has been lost after taking the medication for three months, the course of treatment should be stopped (Ruban et al., 2019).

1.6.3 Bariatric surgery

It is a surgery on the stomach and/or intestines to assist a person suffering from excessive obesity or in losing weight. Bariatric surgery is an option for those with a BMI greater than 40 or from 35 to 40 who have health issues such as type 2 diabetes or heart disease (Feigelson et al., 2020).

The updated guidelines from the American Society of Metabolic and Bariatric Surgery (ASMBS) and the International Federation for the Surgery of Obesity and Metabolic Disorders (IFSO) suggest that individuals with a BMI of ≥ 35 kg/m², regardless of co-morbidities, are now eligible for bariatric surgery. Additionally, those with a BMI of 30-34.9 kg/m², coupled with metabolic disease or obesity-related comorbidities, are also recommended for surgical intervention. This marks a reduction in the threshold for undergoing surgery compared to the previous requirement of a BMI ≥ 40 kg/m² (Hsu et al., 2023).

The 5th edition of the International Federation for the Surgery of Obesity and Metabolic Disorders (IFSO) Global Registry Report documented approximately 800,000 bariatric surgical operations in 61 countries and 17 national registries From 2014 to 2019 (Ramos et al., 2020).

The clinical effectiveness of surgical intervention for treatment of obesity related problems and comorbidities such as diabetes, lipid abnormalities, and hypertension is higher than the non-surgical one (Sjöström, 2013).

There are three main weight-control interventions: (1) diet and exercise treatment modules, (2) medication therapy, and (3) bariatric surgery. Bariatric surgery might result in considerable and sustained weight loss when compared to the other two therapies (Hua et al., 2022).

Bariatric surgery has a massive impact on a variety of aspects of a patient's life (Coulman et al., 2020). In the USA, about 252,000 obese patients receive bariatric surgeries each year, the majority of which are sleeve gastrectomy (SG) and Roux-en-Y gastric bypass (RYGB) operations (Arterburn et al., 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic corresponded for reducing the rate of bariatric surgery from around 256,000 to 199,000 (22.5%) in 2020 (Clapp et al., 2022). For higher-risk obese individuals, bariatric surgeries are a safe and effective strategy (Mechanick et al., 2020).

The success of weight loss following bariatric surgery is impacted by the alteration in gut microbiota due to several factors as the malabsorption status adjustments in the bile acid metabolism, variation in stomach pH, and modifications in the hormone physiology following the bariatric surgery (Ulker & Yildiran, 2019).

The largest single RCT comparing surgical to intensive medical management showed that after 5 years following the bariatric surgery, triglyceride and high-density lipoprotein cholesterol levels markedly decreased from baseline by conducting Roux-en-Y Gastric Bypass intervention followed by moderate reduction using sleeve gastrectomy while a slight effect was noticed when applying medical therapy (Courcoulas et al., 2018).

In comparison to non-surgical methods, bariatric surgery has been shown to higher weight reduction and, more crucially sustaining it over the long term (Wolfe et al., 2016). Therefore, bariatric surgery is currently regarded as the only effective therapy for obesity in individuals with morbid obesity, defined as a body mass index of ≥ 40 or ≥ 35 kg/m² with coexisting health conditions.

1.6.3.1 Types of bariatric surgery

Bariatric procedures fall into one of three categories: Malabsorptive procedures, in which malabsorption is the main cause of weight loss; Restrictive procedures, in which the stomach's capacity is significantly reduced; or Combined procedures, in which elements of both restrictive and malabsorptive procedures are present. The malabsorptive is characterized by bypassing portions of the gastrointestinal system to decrease food

absorption, and the restrictive is characterized by reducing the size of the stomach so that the patient has complied with less amount of food (Padwal et al., 2011) (figure 1.1).

➤ Malabsorptive Interventions as the following:

- **Biliopancreatic diversion (BPD):** where a distal horizontal gastrectomy is performed during the procedure, leaving 200–250 mL of the upper stomach. The distal 250 cm of the small intestine is anastomosed to this residual stomach (alimentary limb). The biliopancreatic limb, or excluded small intestine, which transports bile and pancreatic secretion, is joined to the small bowel 50 cm away from the ileocecal valve. The only portion where digestive secretions and nutrients combine is the 50-cm common limb, which results in notable malabsorption, notably for fat and protein (Lupoli et al., 2017).
- **Roux-en-Y gastric bypass (RYGB):** where the residual stomach and the first loop of the small intestine are bypassed as a result of the formation of a tiny, vertically oriented gastric pouch that is linked to the esophagus at one end and to a short part of the small intestine at the other (Lupoli et al., 2017).

➤ Restrictive Procedures as the following:

- **Sleeve gastrectomy (SG):** where the stomach is divided vertically during the procedure, which lowers its size by 75%. Since the pyloric valve at the base of the stomach is still there, digestion and stomach function are unaffected. The operation is irreversible and may serve as a preparatory step for a duodenal switch or RYGB (Lupoli et al., 2017).
- **Adjustable gastric banding (AGB):** where a 15 to 30 mL gastric pouch is made by encircling the upper stomach with an adjustable silicone band a few millimeters below the cardia. Through an opening positioned in the subcutaneous tissue attached to the band, saline may be injected or removed to alter the outlet's diameter (Lupoli et al., 2017).

Most common weight loss surgery procedures

Figure (1.1): Commonly performed bariatric surgeries.

The top four most popular bariatric procedures, according to the International Federation for the Surgery of Obesity and Metabolic Disorders (IFSO) survey, were laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy (LSG; 53.6%), laparoscopic Roux-en-Y gastric bypass (LRYGB; 30.1%), anastomosis gastric bypass-mini gastric bypass (OAGB; 4.8%), and laparoscopic adjustable gastric banding (LAGB) (Angrisani et al., 2011).

In terms of technical difficulty, laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy (LSG) is simpler than gastric bypass (GB) (Osland et al., 2017) and is thought to carry a reduced risk of postoperative complications (Vidal et al., 2013). In a huge database, The SG accounted for 63% of processes, as opposed to RYGB's 30% and LAGB's 2% (Kizy et al., 2017).

When compared to RYGB, the rise in SG is mostly due to lower complication rates and fewer nutritional deficits (Young et al., 2015). However, a cohort study carried out in Egypt found that after 2-years postoperative follow-up, patients with morbid obesity treated with laparoscopic SG (sleeve gastrectomy) and RYGB did not significantly in terms of amount of weight reduction, resolving medical condition, and improvement in Quality of Life (QoL) (Baheeg et al., 2022).

Weight loss patterns produced by Roux-en-Y gastric bypass (RYGB) are closely related to sleeve gastrectomy (SG) after five years, although duodenal switch (DS) and related operations are linked to the greatest total weight reduction and the best possible resolution of obesity-related comorbidities (Roth et al., 2020). For instance, non-insulin dependent diabetes has a higher chance of experiencing remission after surgery. The risk of developing coronary artery disease (CAD) and needing related treatments, as well as heart failure (HF) are significantly reduced also (Roth et al., 2020).

Similar weight reduction and postoperative complication profiles to those reported in adult populations are seen in adolescent populations following surgical intervention, with better results associated with type 2 Diabetes. As a method of treating obesity and conditions linked to it, bariatric surgery is constantly developing. Despite being beneficial for shedding pounds and curing diseases brought on by obesity, SG is linked to the high incidence of postoperative gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) (Roth et al., 2020).

In the Middle East and North Africa, region bariatric surgery improved patient's mental health, body image, and quality of life (Inocian et al., 2021). In Egypt, a study conducted among 250 patients showed that the percentage of patients who have metabolic syndrome (92%), obesity (100%), diabetes (84%), hypertension (50%), hypertriglyceridemia (74%), and low HDL-cholesterol (50%) was significantly decreased to 17%, 2%, 8%, 17%, 42%, and 25% respectively after one year of follow-up from the bariatric surgery (Bassiony et al., 2019).

1.6.3.2 Bariatric surgery advantages and disadvantages

- Bariatric surgery may lower mortality and promote long-term survival as all-cause mortality was found to be decreased at a median follow-up of 4.9 years after bariatric surgery, especially in men and older patients (Doumouras et al., 2020).
- It is the most successful approach for the treatment of patients suffering from diabetes or hypertension (Gil-Rojas et al., 2019), associated with a 1-year hypertension remission rate ranging from 43% to 83% according to systematic evaluations (Courcoulas et al., 2018). Roux-en-Y Gastric Bypass (RYGB) in individuals with poorly managed diabetes may be beneficial when paired with lifestyle interventions and medicinal therapy (Camilleri & Acosta, 2018). Moreover, surgery is safe and effective in those with compensated cirrhosis who don't have severe portal hypertension. However, it comes with a higher risk of morbidity, and death in those who are liver transplant candidates and/or have severe portal hypertension. The method that seems to work best in this group of patients is vertical sleeve gastrectomy (Cazzo et al., 2017). Furthermore, observational studies indicated that the risk of cancer and osteoarthritis as well as sleep apnea were improved when compared to nonsurgical therapy (Arterburn et al., 2020). Surprisingly, patients with more severe obstructive sleep apnea experienced greater apnea-hypopnea score reductions after bariatric surgery (Kwok et al., 2014).
- Also, the results of eight observational studies proved that bariatric surgery is linked to a lower risk of all cancers (pooled OR, 0.72 [95%CI, 0.59- 0.87]), especially those linked to obesity (pooled OR, 0.55 [95%CI, 0.31-0.96]), including breast cancer (pooled OR, 0.50 [95%CI, 0.25-0.99]) (Schauer et al., 2019; Wiggins et al., 2019; Feigelson et al., 2020).
- In the Swedish Obese Subjects, one of the largest weight-loss studies, which assessed the long-term benefits of several bariatric surgeries, the quality of life significantly improved by reducing cardiovascular events (Kwok et al., 2014). Moreover, bariatric surgery has a good effect on obese patients' psychological health by reducing depression (Fu et al., 2022).
- But one of the main disadvantages is the defective absorption of nutrients and nutritional deficiencies which are significant long-term clinical issues due to changes in the gastrointestinal structure and physiology (Lupoli et al., 2017). Therefore, the best practice guidelines strongly recommend regular metabolic and nutritional monitoring after the procedure with the frequency of assessments that varies depending on the type of the procedure (Mechanick et al., 2020).

1.6.3.3 Cost effectiveness of bariatric surgery

In addition to anticipated health advantages and a decreased risk of complications, bariatric surgery was associated with significant long-term cost savings and greatly improved quality of life (Walter et al., 2022).

A contemporary combination of bariatric surgical techniques among a cohort of Belgian patients was shown to be both cost-effective at 10 years after surgery and cost-saving. In the base-case study over a lifetime horizon, weight loss surgery resulted in cost savings of 9,332 € and added 1.1 years to life as well as 5.0 quality adjusted life years (QALYs). Over a lifetime horizon, bariatric surgery was demonstrated to be a dominating strategy more successful and less expensive than traditional medical care due to superior clinical results and reduced treatment costs (Borisenko et al., 2018).

Bariatric surgery was found to be economically advantageous in all trials including obese people with diabetes. In Thailand's setting, using bariatric surgery on patients who were extremely obese and have type 2 diabetes was an economically cost effective choice because the incremental cost of bariatric surgery per QALY when compared to pharmaceutical treatment for diabetes was a more affordable alternative (Viratanapanu et al., 2019).

When weight loss lasted for more than five years, gastric bypass bariatric surgery for type 2 diabetes who were overweight but not obese looked to be financially advantageous (Wentworth et al., 2017).

For an obese Colombian cohort suffering from diabetes and hypertension, bariatric surgery was a more cost-effective option, with an incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) of \$6 194 899 and \$43 689 527 per QALY gained, respectively, and an ICER less than the 3 gross national product (GNP) per capita threshold (\$49 841 853) (Gil-Rojas et al., 2019).

Generally, patients with comorbidities associated with obesity may find bariatric surgery to be a financially viable option. As following bariatric surgery, a considerable decrease in post-operative drug costs, outpatient clinic visits, and inpatient hospitalizations have been seen at King Khalid University Hospital, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia (Dohayan Al-Dohayan et al., 2021).

According to economic modelling research that compared the surgery to community weight control, bariatric surgery was a very cost-effective treatment option for idiopathic intracranial hypertension in obese women. The model demonstrated that having surgery resulted in long-term cost savings and health advantages, but that these benefits did not begin to appear until five years after the procedure and steadily grew over time (Elliot et al., 2021).

Also, patients with non-alcoholic steatohepatitis cirrhosis or compensated cirrhosis, and suffering from obesity, or overweight found bariatric surgery to be very cost-effective (Klebanoff et al., 2019).

Comparing surgery to non-surgical therapy, the long-term incremental cost-utility ratios ranged from \$ 1,000 to \$40,000 (USD) every quality-adjusted life year (QALY) and with a willingness-to-pay threshold of £25,000/QALY. Bariatric surgery outperformed standard therapy (Padwal et al., 2011).

Bariatric surgery was cost-effective in high-income countries among mixed obesity groups (i.e., obesity with or without diabetes), over a 10-year time horizon and lifetime horizon. Nevertheless, there is no evidence in low- and middle-income nations (Noparatayaporn et al., 2021)

1.6.3.4 Patient preference

Bariatric surgery patients and clinicians may benefit from shared decision making. Combining patient values and preferences with current medical knowledge helps in the difficult bariatric surgery selection process and assists the government system in allocating resources (Weinstein et al., 2014). There was a similarity between patient choices and surgeon preferences when asked to stand in the place of their patients except for some variations, particularly those linked to sensitivity to the risk of complications and out-of-pocket expenditures (Rozier et al., 2020).

While there seems to be too little material particularly designed to facilitate patient engagement, doctors believe that a lack of appropriate information or access to it is a barrier to shared decision making (Coulter et al., 1999). Doctors should be aware of their patients' preferences to give better treatment. For doctors, this poses several difficulties. Time constraints and challenges in obtaining preferences from patients who might be unwilling to make treatment decisions are examples of practical obstacles.

For the patients, satisfactory information supply about the operation is founded on three principles: verifying patients' knowledge of the offered information during the consult, discussing the impact of surgery on their everyday life, and approaching them as humans (Coblijn et al., 2018).

A lack of key information to assist patients' decisions worsens these problems. It's possible that medical professionals lack the necessary interpersonal skills, especially in communication (Say & Thomson, 2003).

The results of a narrative literature analysis that sought to compare how patients and consumers make decisions and to find consumer research techniques that may be used to elicit patient preferences showed that patients might be viewed as a subgroup of consumers due to parallels in their decision-making processes, indicating that consumer preference elicitation principles may be applicable in the medical field. However, it is still unclear how closely real decision-making situations may be reproduced in the healthcare industry (Ver Donck et al., 2020).

Conjoint analysis is widely used by marketing researchers and economists, and it is based on both theoretical premises and actual findings (Hensher et al., 2005). An important method for determining people's preferences for health services is conjoint analysis (CA). The decision-making processes that impact real-world choices are more precisely approximated by adaptive choice based conjoint analysis (ACBC) surveys (Cunningham et al., 2010).

Recently adaptive choice based conjoint (ACBC) which was developed by "Sawtooth Software" (a vendor of CA software packages) has gained more popularity (Fraenkel, 2008; Cunningham et al., 2010; Al-Omari et al., 2022). Adaptive CBC is a novel and promising approach, as it simulated the whole selection process and produced data that was more accurate and predictive for the real choice behavior.

ACBC would provide comparable group-level standard errors, with 38% fewer respondents than a choice based conjoint survey, according to Chapman et al. In health service situations where it may be challenging to assemble patient samples big enough to perform standard choice based CA surveys, smaller sample sizes may make these approaches more valuable and compensate for the longer time needed to perform adaptive choice based conjoint analysis (ACBC) (Cunningham et al., 2010).

ACBC interview was more engaging and realistic than the typical CBC interview as the included tasks were tailored at the individual level to include winning concepts from the prior one, also it offered more precise predictions. Despite it was twice longer than the conventional CBC questionnaire, the respondents expressed the same level of satisfaction (Orme & Johnson, 2008).

To our knowledge no study in Egypt used a novel technique like adaptive choice based conjoint analysis to individually determine patient preference and part worth utility so we decided to use the adaptive choice based conjoint analysis to reveal the more important bariatric surgery attributes for the Egyptian obese patients which will aid in better understanding for the process of patients' decision making.

AIM OF THE STUDY

This study aims to measure obese patient's preferences for the risks, benefits, and other attributes of bariatric surgery in a group of patients who are candidates for bariatric surgery in Alexandria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Selecting a bariatric procedure should be based on individualized goals of therapy (e.g., weight loss, improvements in specific medical conditions), available local-regional expertise (obesity specialists, bariatric surgeons, and institutions), patients' preferences, personalized risk stratification that prioritizes safety (Mechanick et al., 2020).

Patients may benefit from shared decision making, which incorporates patient values and preferences along with current medical evidence to assist in the challenging process of selecting a bariatric surgery procedure (Weinstein et al., 2014).

Self-selected bariatric procedures produced excellent weight loss and metabolic outcomes, according to an assessment study conducted in 2017 by a multidisciplinary team that compared the safety and outcomes of laparoscopic Roux-en-Y gastric bypass (LRYGB) to those of laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy (LSG) and adjustable gastric band (AGB) in a single center, among the 303 patients who made their own choice of procedure. Giving patients access to a wealth of information enhances their decision-making over their procedure and increases their willingness to comply with the weight loss surgery program (Vasas et al., 2018).

Many studies examined obese patients' preferences for bariatric surgery worldwide and some of them mainly focus on dividing them into special groups such as male and female or based on the type of comorbidity such as diabetes.

We systematically searched Medline/PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science on July 15, 2022; and found a large number of studies from 2005 to 2022 about obese patients' preferences for bariatric surgery that focused on checking knowledge, perceptions, and attitudes. There were two main methods to test patient's preferences such as preference exploration techniques and elicitation methods. The first are qualitative approaches that gather descriptive information about a phenomenon or a participant by observing and focusing on their subjective experiences and choices. Whereas, the second methods are quantitative collecting measurable data for statistical analysis and hypothetical testing (Beshears et al., 2008; Lambooi et al., 2015).

We divided the studies into the following groups according to the method used to access the preference into the following:

1. Studies that employed preference exploration methods such as the survey, interviews, and focus groups (19 studies).
2. Studies that used preference elicitation methods such as discrete choice experiment (DCE) (2 studies).

2.1. Studies that used preference exploration methods:

2.1.1 Studies used the survey method:

Multiple choice questions were used to determine the preferences for different bariatric surgeries (gastric bypass, gastric sleeve, gastric banding) in addition to explore the factors that influenced the patients' choice of surgeon, and surgery as well as their preference for short or long-term expected outcomes among 1,300 participants in Saudi Arabia. The study discovered that in thirty percent of participants, good appearance and body fitness were the most important considered outcomes after the surgery. Important factors when giving a higher preference for a particular type of surgery were less side effects, more weight loss, a recovery period after the surgery, and advice from friends. The most refined procedure was sleeve gastrectomy, which was expected to yield the maximum weight loss. The major downside was that it ignored the effect of diet and lifestyle activity programs. The generalizability of the research results was affected due to the nature of the study design which was a cross-sectional study with a structured framework questionnaire (Mahfouz et al., 2021).

Open-ended questions were self-administered to 159 participants in the obesity Clinic in Norway to highlight what influenced the preferences of severely obese patients deciding whether to undergo gastric bypass surgery or make lifestyle changes, and whether the number of diseases affects patient's motivation. Patients who believed that their diseases would increase the risk of complications during the surgery were more willing to apply lifestyle modification treatment over conducting a bariatric surgery. However, bariatric surgery was a great choice among those whose physical activities were impaired by their diseases (Strømme et al., 2009).

A validated adapted closed end questionnaire was administered in a single bariatric surgical unit. The 5-point Likert scales were used to determine patient awareness, views, and priorities for bariatric surgery outcomes among 150 patients in the UK. The study discovered that complication and reoperation rates were the top outcome measures from the patient's perspective. However, several kinds of bias defected this cross-sectional questionnaire study such as recall and sample bias (Lam et al., 2022).

A multilingual questionnaire associated with a 5-point Likert scale was used to identify patient's preferences of the various outcomes and complications for bariatric surgeries between 172 patients in the USA. Greatest weight loss was the most considered parameter among the majority of patients while individuals suffering from diabetes were more concerned with diabetes remission. However, the study was unable to account for external factors that influence decision making such as family, friends, the internet, and media as well as the integration of outcomes and complications to rationalise the procedure chosen by the patient (Weinstein et al., 2014).

A 27 item questionnaire was administrated to 356 qualified patients in a teaching hospital and a bariatric center in Amsterdam (Netherlands), to assess bariatric surgery patients' preferences for information provided prior to the surgery. The study concluded that information regarding the effects of the operation on daily life was the most important to consider. Whereas the value of information about the associated complication decreased if the incidence of the complication is low (Coblijn et al., 2018).

A questionnaire with 5 points Likert scale was used to evaluate risk perception of bariatric surgery and related comorbidities (heart disease, type 2 diabetes mellitus, systemic hypertension, sleep apnea, and dyslipidemia) among 128 obese patients at a tertiary care center for treatment of obesity in Brazil. When the patients sought treatment for obesity with comorbidities linked to more advanced stages of the disease, men were more likely than women to perceive the risk of heart disease and mortality from surgical complications (Schakarowski et al., 2018).

While another study conducted in three bariatric centers and the university hospital Heidelberg in Germany among 248 patients using the same tool to assess patient's expectations about bariatric surgery between different genders revealed that for both males and females improvement of health conditions was the most critical outcome (Fischer et al., 2014).

Also, willingness to pay (WTP) questionnaires were given to 100 of patients at the obesity and bariatric surgery outpatient clinic of the Federal University of Sao Paulo (Brazil) including two formats of contingent valuation questions: dichotomous choice (yes/no) and a bidding game to assess their preferences for surgical obesity treatment. Existing comorbidities drove their decision making especially sleep apnea which had the greatest impact. However, the sample was restricted to patients who already expressed a preference to bariatric surgery, which biased the generalizability of the results (Khawali et al., 2014).

Using a multiple-choice questionnaire and 5-point Likert scales, 150 obese patients in a diabetic outpatient clinic in Singapore were asked about their thoughts and worries about bariatric surgery as a therapeutic option for their condition. The most important parameters to consider from their point of view were surgical complications, length of recovery period, and the persistence of gained benefits. A main weakness in the study was the small sample size (Chua et al., 2016).

Sixty-four items survey including the decisional conflict scale, decision self-efficacy scale, EuroQol 5D, and the standard gamble was given to 200 subjects during a meeting of a bariatric surgery interest group held in a university hospital in the United States. Patient's perceptions about their current quality of life strongly affected the decision to have bariatric surgery. Not all of the patients were extremely obese but only interested in having bariatric surgery which mainly affected the validity of the results (Schauer et al., 2014).

A retrospective population-based survey with multiple choice questions and a 5-point Likert scale was used to assess the risk perception of 273 obese patients undergoing bariatric surgery at the Mayo nutrition clinic in the United States. The results showed that the risk of not losing weight was viewed as being higher than the risk of having the procedure. However, the lack of BMI or any adiposity indicator in risk assessments was a limitation in this study (Prasad et al., 2014).

In the USA, a survey was conducted by a university-based health system among 130 patients with type 2 diabetes and body mass index (BMI) between 30 and 40 kg/m². The opinions about having bariatric surgery to manage their health condition were examined. Few diabetic patients who were obese believed that the surgery will improve their health condition. The main weakness was the low response rate (25.3%) as those who replied might have been more biased toward bariatric surgery (Sarwer et al., 2013).

In a cross-sectional online survey with 104 patients in Korea, the candidates for bariatric surgery preferred sleeve gastrectomy (SG), followed by adjustable gastric banding (AGB), gastric plication (GP), and Roux-en-Y gastric bypass (RYGB), and the main justifications for choosing the procedures were: "adjustable" for AGB, "stomach sparing" for GP, "great weight loss" for SG, and "resolution of comorbidity" in RYGB. But all the respondents were online users which may drawback the generalizability (Roh et al., 2020).

2.1.2 Studies that used the interview method:

Using Face to face interview in 2 major bariatric surgical centres among 469 consecutive patients in the United States (n = 124) and Australia (n = 345) to determine factors affecting their choice for a particular bariatric operation. It was discovered that safety and invasiveness had the greatest influence on patient's decisions in both countries (Ren et al., 2005).

A qualitative study conducted among 73 patients in the USA who underwent semi-structured interviews reported that the most significant components of bariatric surgery from the patient's perspective were the risk of complications, followed by dietary changes and the percentage of weight loss. But in this study, since men made up the majority of participants, it's likely that their findings did not fully reflect how was the difference in gender perception (Murtha et al., 2022).

A semi-structured interpersonal interview of 29 obese females where Indigenous patients revealed that improvement of medical condition, along with quality of life, are the most important bariatric surgery outcomes. However, the small sample size was a limitation (Rahiri et al., 2019).

Telephone interview was conducted among 298 patients at two university hospitals in Boston USA. The main factors that determined whether patients would choose to perform gastric banding instead of gastric bypass surgery were diabetic condition, quality of life, eating habits, target weight loss, and willingness to accept mortality risk. The generalizability of the findings may be constrained since that, despite the study was conducted at two academic institutions, but both were in Boston (Apovian et al., 2013).

Using a computer-assisted telephone interview in a large integrated healthcare system in the Southern California region of the United States among 1,975 participants to measure food preferences following bariatric surgery, it was obvious that Roux-en-Y gastric bypass (RYGB) may be associated with major alteration in taste and liking of particular types of foods compared to sleeve gastrectomy. Due to the nature of the used instrument, which was designed for post-operative taste assessment only, it did not provide an accurate measurement over time. In addition, recall bias occurred when asking patients to compare their current state to the previous one (Lewis et al., 2021).

2.1.3. Study that used focus group method:

Using Open-ended questions in six focus group sessions in the United States, a qualitative analysis was conducted on 41 obese African American (AA) women's perceptions of barriers to weight loss and bariatric surgery. The most important aspects from their perspective were the risk of complications associated with the amount of weight loss, as well as physical and lifestyle restrictions. Because the study focused on AA women in one location beside their small sample size, the findings may not be generalizable. Additionally, it did not examine how views alter when the patient take the therapeutic decisions which may affect the results (Lynch et al., 2007).

There are numerous various ways to evaluate patient's revealed preferences; yet, the application of revealed-preference approaches still faces methodological challenges in the health field (Janssens et al., 2019).

Conjoint analysis (CA) methodology employs three basic approaches such as ranking, rating, or discrete choices to identify patient preferences (Ryan & Farrar, 2000). CA was becoming more popular in healthcare as a beneficial approach for identifying patient's preferences and WTP (Al-Omari et al., 2022). Unlike standard questionnaires, patients must trade off benefits, frequency, side effects and make some sacrifices when conducting conjoint study as it provides multiple hypothetical scenarios and asks them to rate, rank, or choose their preferable one (Al-Omari & McMeekin, 2020).

2.1.4. Studies used preference elicitation methods (discrete choice conjoint analysis)

In the United States, a discrete choice experiment was used to identify surgeon preferences for risks, benefits, and other attributes for bariatric surgery. Results were compared with patient preferences. A strong alignment between the two preferences was found when surgeons were asked to stand in the place of their patients. Despite there were some differences, as surgeons chose profiles with a lower risk of complications and were less sensitive to out-of-pocket cost than patients (Rozier et al., 2020).

Discrete choice analysis was applied on 815 patients to determine patient preferences for risks, benefits, and other characteristics of treatment choices available to candidates for bariatric surgery. Surgical cost, anticipated weight reduction, and resolution of medical conditions were the most relevant factors in weight loss surgery decision making. Whereas the risk of complications and unpleasant consequences were less important from the patient's point of view. This type of conjoint analysis was unsuitable due to the large number of included nine attributes, along with the complexity of the choice question which needed to be simplified throughout the selection process (Rozier et al., 2019).

Compared to standard CBC the adaptive method collected more information at the individual level to estimate partworths utilities so it can be used with a smaller sample size. Beside that, it was the best choice when we had a large number of attributes five or more (Cunningham et al., 2010). Utility estimates produced by ACBC and CBC were highly compatible, however utility beta values resulted from ACBC had lower standard deviation, suggesting that with smaller sample sizes it was able to provide reliable results. In addition, the actual decision-making process was more representative by using ACBC instead of CBC (Chapman et al., 2009).

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials and methods chapter consists of the following sections:

- 3.1. Study design, setting, and population.
- 3.2. The adaptive choice based conjoint analysis experiment.
 - 3.2.1. Identifying and selection of attributes.
 - 3.2.2. ACBC survey sections
 - 3.2.3. Experimental design
 - 3.2.4. Instrumental design
 - 3.2.5. Data collection, Sample size, Ethics
- 3.3. Statistical Analysis

3.1. Study design, setting, and population.

3.1.1. Study design

Cross-sectional survey

3.1.2. Study setting:

We conducted the study at Alexandria Medical Research Institute's bariatric surgery clinic.

3.1.3. Study population:

Obese patients seeking weight loss at the bariatric surgery clinic of the Medical Research Institute, Alexandria University for 6 months (from 10th November 2021 to 20th May 2022).

Inclusion criteria

Obese patients with BMI of ≥ 35 kg/m², regardless of co-morbidities. Additionally, those with a BMI of 30-34.9 kg/m², coupled with metabolic disease or obesity-related comorbidities aged between 18 and 60 years old.

Exclusion criteria

Presence of any cognitive impairment, or disease that could hinder their ability to express their preferences.

3.1.4 Sampling Technique:

We identified eligible obese participants through their visits to the bariatric surgery clinic. Our sampling strategy consisted of:

- A sample was taken from obese patients who visited the bariatric surgery clinic of the medical research institute between 10 November 2021 and 20 May 2022. A face-to-face interview was carried out on various weekdays between 9 am and 3 pm and 10 patients on average were interviewed each day.

- The interviewer took precautions against COVID-19 transmission by meeting the patients in a private, comfortable, and well-ventilated room to conduct face to face computer aided interview.

3.1.4.1 Sample size calculation:

Sawtooth software which specialized in designing and conducting adaptive choice based conjoint analysis was used to determine the appropriate sample size. The software determined a minimum sample size of 250 respondents required for modelling based on nine attributes, fifteen tasks per respondent, and three alternatives per screening section beside two alternatives per choice tournament section.

3.2. The adaptive choice based conjoint experiment.

To study obese patients' preferences for the bariatric surgery, we conducted an adaptive choice based conjoint experiment following the guidance of the International Society of Pharmacoeconomics and Outcomes Research (ISPOR), good research practices that aimed to standardize the methods used for conjoint analysis in healthcare research (Bridges et al., 2011).

3.2.1 Identification and Selection of Attributes and their levels

Through literature review, we detected six studies (Mühlbacher & Bethge, 2013; Whitty et al., 2015; Rozier et al., 2019; Donnan et al., 2020; Queally et al., 2020; Rozier et al., 2020) that evaluated patients' preferences for bariatric surgery through conjoint analysis. The attributes and levels were identified based on their prevalence, applicability to our research and clinical based discussion with experts in the field. To validate the usage of ACBC method in our study we tested the 8 points that were recommended in the Sawtooth checklist as shown in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Sawtooth recommended 8 Points to Be Checked in ACBC study

Question	Answer
Is this an appropriate study for ACBC? Appropriate studies typically involve about five or more attributes.	Yes. 9 attributes included.
Have you used the Test Design capability on the Design tab to have the software generate dummy (robotic) respondents that answer randomly? Have you examined the attribute level frequency report for these dummy test records? Does each non-BYO level occur at a minimum of 2 times (3 times, preferably)?	Yes. The design was tested, and each response was appeared 2 times for the dummy respondents
Does each respondent evaluate no more than about 7 levels per attribute?	Yes. The maximum number of levels per attribute was 4.
If you are studying a large number of attributes or levels per attribute (such that using constructed lists to discard levels and attributes from consideration within the ACBC survey is necessary), is your sample size sufficient to stabilize the parameters across the full list of attributes and levels? Are you willing to assume that discarded attributes are entirely unimportant to the respondent?	No, we use appropriate number of attributes
When you take the questionnaire, do the Unacceptable and Must-Have questions properly identify (using correct “at least” or “at most” phrasing) the levels you have consistently selected or rejected? (This confirms you set the correct worst to best or best to worst attribute direction).	Yes. We used the ideal keywords to identify the Unacceptable and Must-Have questions
Take a practice questionnaire yourself, making sure that the computed part-worths reflect the preferences you expressed in the questionnaire	Yes. The questionnaire was tested, and the produced part-worth utility truly reflects the patient's preference.
Have you asked colleagues or a small convenience sample of target respondents to take the survey? Have you debriefed them regarding their experiences and analyzed their data? Were any sections/instructions confusing? Do the computed part-worth utilities reasonably reflect their individual preferences? Confusing? Do the computed part-worth utilities reasonably reflect their individual preferences?	Yes. A convenience sample tested the questionnaire in the pilot study and reflected their experience. The computed part-worth utility truly reflects their preference
Have you fielded the study (a “soft launch”) among a few target respondents, examining the same issues as directly above?	Yes. this was tested in the pilot study by both of convenience sample and expert in the field .

The following nine attributes were used to describe each surgical procedure: (1) How the surgery will help you to lose weight, (2) Surgery magnitude (recovery and reversibility), (3) Surgery availability (number of years since the treatment has been available), (4) Number of kilograms you prefer to lose in year 1 and the regained percentage of them in year 2, (5) Improvement of weight associated medical condition, (6) Risk of complications within 3 years, (7) Adverse effects, (8) Diet changes, and (9) Initial out of pocket costs including surgery and follow up. Each attribute had four levels except for Initial out of pocket costs including surgery and follow up attribute which had three levels.

3.2.2 The adaptive Choice based Conjoint (ACBC) survey consisted of four sections:

- **Sociodemographic characteristics:** including age, gender, employment status, marital status, household income, educational level, BMI, and health condition.
- **Build Your Own section (BYO):** it collects data on how participants combine features to create their ideal products and services by presenting a comprehensive list of features along with their corresponding levels and for each feature, participants must select the most preferred level at each attribute. (Figure 3.1) (Orme, 2014).
- **Screening section:** various profiles are generated randomly by combining attributes and levels. Each profile is evaluated by the participants. Based on the screening data, we determine which features and levels are most influential on participants' decisions. Based on a selection of the most relevant features and levels, a choice task is then prepared. Screening is intended to reduce the number of features and levels required for choice tasks, reducing the complexity of the conjoint analysis, and improving the quality of the data. (Figure 3.2) (Orme, 2014).
- **The Choice Tournament section:** respondents are considering concepts that are close to the BYO-specified product, that they consider as "possibilities," and that strictly comply with any cut-off criteria (must have/unacceptable). The greyed-out levels are intended to facilitate information processing so respondents can concentrate on the remaining differences rather than those tied across concepts as the ACBC design is based on a fractional factorial design, the participants are not

presented with every possible combination of features and levels, thus reducing the cognitive load on participants, and ensuring accurate and reliable data collection. According to each respondent's previous choices, Sawtooth software's ACBC module dynamically constructs choice tasks for them. A Choice Tournament is typically designed in such a way that participants are shown each product profile several times in pairs, ensuring that the data collected is reliable and accurate. A choice tournament can be useful for determining which features and levels customers value most and identifying the most appealing combinations of them (Figure 3.3) (Orme, 2014).

In this scenario you are going to conduct a bariatric surgery , what is the maximum outcome you prefer to get in each feature please select one from each drop down lists

Feature	Select features
How the surgery will help you to lose weight	<input type="radio"/> Reduces calories minimize exercise and behavior modification <input type="radio"/> Restrict amount of food that can be eaten at one time may not decrease hunger <input type="radio"/> Restricts amount of food that can be eaten at one time decrease hunger <input type="radio"/> Restrict amount of food decrease hunger reduce absorption of nutrients from food
surgery magnitude	<input type="radio"/> No recovery needed , the procedure is reversible <input type="radio"/> You will need one week to recover from the procedure , the procedure is reversible <input type="radio"/> You will need two weeks to recover from the procedure , the procedure is permanent <input type="radio"/> You will need four weeks to recover from the procedure , the procedure is reversible in rare cases
Since how long the surgery has been available to patients	<input type="radio"/> 1 year availability <input type="radio"/> 5 years availability <input type="radio"/> 10 years availability <input type="radio"/> 20 years availability
Number of Kg you prefer to lose in year 1 and regain percentage of them in year 2	<input type="radio"/> Lose 40% excess body weight Kgs in year 1 and regain 20% of them in year 2 <input type="radio"/> Loss 40 %excess body weight kgs in year 1 and regain 0%of them in year 2 <input type="radio"/> Loss 80% excess body weight kgs in year 1 and regain 20% of them in year 2 <input type="radio"/> Loss 80%excess body weight kgs in year 1 and regain 0%of them in year 2
Diet changes	<input type="radio"/> Normal foods with small portion, buy vitamins <input type="radio"/> No restriction <input type="radio"/> Calories restricted must buy special food <input type="radio"/> Avoid food high in fat and sugar levels buy supplements

Figure (3.1): An example of a "BYO question" from the ACBC task, note that attributes with ordered preference did not include to decrease the complexity and they will be included in the screening section .

Here are 3 lists including few treatment criteria you might like. For each list , indicate whether it is a possibility or not.

(1 of 6)

Reduces calories minimize exercise and behavior modification	Restrict amount of food that can be eaten at one time may not decrease hunger	Reduces calories minimize exercise and behavior modification
You will need one week to recover from the procedure , the procedure is reversible	You will need four weeks to recover from the procedure , the procedure is reversible in rare cases	No recovery needed , the procedure is reversible
5 years availability	10 years availability	1 year availability
Loss 80% excess body weight kgs in year 1 and regain 20% of them in year 2	Lose 40% excess body weight Kgs in year 1 and regain 20% of them in year 2	Loss 40 % excess body weight kgs in year 1 and regain 0% of them in year 2
Still have hypertansion or sleep apnea <u>but no</u> diabetes or high cholesterol	Still have diabetes high cholesterol levels hypertention or sleep apnea	still have diabetes <u>but no</u> hypertention sleep apnea high cholesterol levels
5 % risk of complication	20% risk of complication	35% risk of complication
No adverse effects	Malabsorption can result in hair and bone loss	Nausea vomiting, acid reflux ,stomach pain
Normal foods with small portion,buy vitamins	Normal foods with small portion,buy vitamins	Calories restricted must buy special food
50000 EGP	65000 EGP	65000 EGP
<input type="radio"/> A possibility <input type="radio"/> Won't work for me	<input type="radio"/> A possibility <input type="radio"/> Won't work for me	<input type="radio"/> A possibility <input type="radio"/> Won't work for me

Figure (3.2): An example of a "Screening Question" from the ACBC task.

Among these two lists of treatment criteria , please choose which is the best list for you ? (I've grayed out any features that are the same, so you can just focus on the differences.)

(1 of 4)

Reduces calories minimize exercise and behavior modification	Reduces calories minimize exercise and behavior modification
You will need one week to recover from the procedure , the procedure is reversible	No recovery needed , the procedure is reversible
1 year availability	10 years availability
Loss 40 %excess body weight kgs in year 1 and regain 0%of them in year 2	Loss 80% excess body weight kgs in year 1 and regain 20% of them in year 2
Still have hypertansion or sleep apnea <u>but no</u> diabetes or high cholesterol	No diabetes high cholesterol levels hypertension or sleep apnea
0 % risk of complication	35% risk of complication
Malabsorption can result in hair and bone loss	Malabsorption can result in hair and bone loss
Normal foods with small portion,buy vitamins	Avoid food high in fat and sugar levels buy supplements
35000 EGP	35000 EGP
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Figure (3.3): An example of a "Choice question" from the ACBC task.

3.2.3 Experimental design

ACBC experiments can be designed using a full-factorial design or a fractional-factorial design. The fractional-factorial design was used in our study; this design used only a fraction of the possible pairwise comparisons between the different combinations of attribute's levels. It provided an estimate of the main effects.

We used sawtooth software to generate the experimental design as follows:

1. Attribute and level selection: creating an ACBC survey begins with entering the attribute lists and levels (Orme, 2014).
2. Construction of the choice tasks: each respondent's choice task is dynamically constructed based on his previous choices using an adaptive design algorithm. It is possible to specify how many alternatives there are per task in the BYO task, as well as how many choice tasks are available per respondent, including the screening and choice tournament sections (Orme, 2014).
3. Randomization and blocking: randomization and blocking of choice tasks are available so that order effects can be minimized (Orme, 2014).

The design included 15 different blocks randomly assigned to the respondents including one BYO task followed by 8 screener sections combined with must have and unacceptable questions to exclude certain attributes from the last stage which is the choice tournament task that consisted of 6 different blocks. The total number of alternatives in the 15 blocks varied from 3 alternatives at the screener section to 2 alternatives at the choice tournament section.

ACBC has a number of desirable design properties that are recommended by the International Society for Pharmacoeconomics and Outcomes Research (ISPOR) to maximize statistical efficiency (Bridges et al., 2011). These properties include:

1. Orthogonality: to reduce the complexity of the data and ensure that each attribute is evaluated independently of all the others this helped to estimate main effects without interference from interaction effects.
2. Balance: respondents receive an equal representation of attribute levels across various profiles at an equal number of times which prevents systematic bias.

3. Minimal Overlap: it refers to avoiding overlap between levels of different attributes within a profile to increase response precision and reduce confusion among respondents.
4. Level Ordering: the ordering of attribute levels should be random to avoid bias.
5. Efficient Design: method for estimating the most important parameters by asking the fewest questions possible to reduce the burden on respondents as the process of data collection will be faster and more accurate when the design is efficient.
6. Robustness: design's ability to produce accurate results even when potential errors or violations of assumptions are present.

Sawtooth Software creates designs that meet these criteria and maximize statistical efficiency. Also, the software allows for the customization of the design (Sawtooth Software, 2021).

3.2.4 Instrument Design

Pilot test:

A pilot test on 25 patients was made to reach an optimal instrument design. These patients were excluded from the analysis. The findings of which made us able to:

- Developing a design that is suitable for respondents and does not hinder quality by having too many screening or choice tasks.
- Finding out how many tasks can be performed without the patients becoming mentally exhausted.
- Making the questions short and informative to maximize their effectiveness.
- Evaluating cognitive load and response time.

Our initial instrument used in pilot testing consisted of:

- A consent form with an introduction about the study and its purpose.
- A questionnaire about the respondents' sociodemographic characteristics.

- The ACBC's questionnaire which consisted of the BYO, screening, and choice tournament tasks generated by lighthouse studio (Sawtooth software) to measure obese patient's preference for bariatric surgery.

After testing that instrument, we found a high level of burden and mental exhaustion on the respondents, so we modified the instrument as follows:

- A reduction in the number of tasks, such as from 12 to 8 in the screening section and from 8 to 6 in the choice tournament section, after that the consistency and quality of responses were tested to make sure that each attribute's level appeared at least twice to the participant.
- The ACBC questionnaire has been improved by adding visual aids and clear instructions to ensure respondents understand the task and provide reliable responses.

Our final instrument consisted of an interview led survey with four sections:

- Informed consent with a copy given to the respondent.
- Sociodemographic survey
- The ACBC questionnaire which consisted of three main parts dependent on each other BYO, screening, and choice tournament sections.
- The interview was conducted on the computer and all the responses were recorded on the sawtooth software server.

3.2.5 Ethical considerations

For participation in the survey, informed consent from patients was obtained in conjunction with the data collection forms following the guidelines of the ethical review board in the Medical Research Institute.

3.3 Statistical analysis

3.3.1 Sociodemographic characteristic analysis

SPSS (version 28.0.0.0) was used to describe the categorical data of the sample characteristics such as age, gender, employment status, marital status, household income, educational level, BMI, and health condition using the percentage and frequency.

3.3.2 Adaptive choice based conjoint analysis.

The conditional logit model was used in Adaptive Choice based Conjoint analysis (ACBC) to evaluate the relative impact of various features and levels on participants' choices. The model presumes that participants choose features based on a mix of their levels plus a random error term. Maximum likelihood estimation was used in the conditional logit model to estimate the relative importance of each attribute. The utility of any product profile is a linear function of the levels of its attributes. The model was used to estimate part-worth utilities for each attribute level which represents the relative value that consumers place on different levels of each attribute in an additive way to predict consumer choices (Orme, 2010).

The relative importance of each attribute in conjoint analysis is determined by considering the extent to which each attribute contributes to the total utility of a product. This contribution is measured by the range of utility values associated with each attribute. By calculating percentages based on the relative ranges, we obtain a set of attribute importance values that sum up to 100 percent. These importance values provide insights into the significance of each attribute in influencing consumer preferences within the conjoint analysis (Orme, 2019).

We used the following formula for the calculation of the attributes' relative importance (Orme, 2019)

$$\text{Relative Importance (\%)} = (\text{Range of Attribute Utility} / \text{Total Range of Utility}) * 100$$

Part-worths utilities are estimated by averaging the scores assigned to different attribute levels. These utilities effectively predict individual respondents' preferences for products (Orme, 2014). The scaling of conjoint utilities is influenced by the experimental designs used in conjoint analysis and the dummy coding in the design matrix. In particular, when effects coding, a specific type of dummy coding, is employed, the utilities are scaled to sum up to zero within each attribute (Orme, 2019). Often, utility estimates obtained from conjoint analysis surveys require fine-tuning. This fine-tuning involves adjusting the utilities by a constant factor to enhance their predictive accuracy compared to actual market outcomes (Orme & Heft, 1999).

3.3.3 Utility values statistical analysis

Sawtooth Software calculates utility values at each attribute level by using hierarchical Bayesian analysis to estimate parameters at multiple levels of analysis (Orme, 2000).

- At the individual respondent level, the analysis estimates individual-level parameters that reflect the preferences of each respondent for the attributes and levels of the product profile to estimate the individual overall utility.
- At the aggregate level, all respondents in the study are aggregated to estimate utility values based on attribute level combinations, to identify the most important attributes and levels.

Sawtooth light house studio using ACBC/Hierarchical Baye (HB) logit model (software, version 13.5 Sawtooth Software; Orem, UT, USA) [Software S.2016] to calculate part-worths utilities by the following multiple regression models:

$$Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + \dots + b_nX_n$$

Y = dependent variable (utility)

b₀ = constant

b₁...b_n = regression weights (betas)

X₁...X_n = independent variables

3.3.3 Construction of the clusters

Clustering approach, particularly the most well-known of the partitioning-based clustering methods employ centroids for grouping. K-means is an iterative algorithm that divides N items into K distinct groups. K-means is possibly the most extensively used (Estivill-Castro, 2002). Convergent Cluster & Ensemble Analysis (CCEA) program that belong to Sawtooth software was used to conduct k-mean clustering analysis and produced two clusters with a higher percentage of reproducibility 98.7% (Risk averse VS Risk taker).

This is how the technique is put into practice:

- Minimizing the total distance between the members of a group and its corresponding centroid (Slonim et al., 2013).
- Reducing the within-cluster sum of squares (WCSS) which measures the quality of k-means clustering (Yuan & Yang, 2019).

The " k-means " algorithm is an effective method of performing cluster analysis (Orme & Johnson, 2008); which depends on :

- Consider seeds as potential cluster centers.
- Identify the nearest seed for each respondent.
- Recalculate resulting cluster centers.
- Repeat steps 2 and 3 until no changes in respondents' classification.

In our study, we used the k-mean clustering method with the following settings:

- Minimum group number was 2 and maximum was 5.
- Minimum group size: 1
- Number of replications: 30
- Maximum number of iterations: 1000
- No outliers

- Random number seed: 1
- Mix of starting points:
 - Distance based: used distant respondents as a starting point.
 - Density based: utilized populous regions as starting points for seeds.
 - Hierarchical based: employed the centroids produced by the hierarchical clusteranalysis as seeds.

Each value associated with a certain profile displays the mean centroid value calculated from all occurrences associated with that profile; the greater the value, the higher the likelihood that it will be significant to consumers (Sirait et al., 2017).

3.3.4 Statistical analysis of the clusters

The utility values were described by mean and 95% CI. The Pearson chi-square X^2 was used to capture the characteristics of the risk-averse and risk-taker groups and the odds ratio of the univariate. Logistic regression and its 95% CI was used to test for the likelihood of being a risk taker. Comparison of the attribute's importance and utility values between risk averse and risk taker was performed by the independent t-test combined with either Cohen's d or point estimate.

Cohen's d is a statistical measure that quantifies the standardized mean difference of an effect. It is commonly employed to facilitate comparisons of effects across studies, even when the dependent variables are measured using different approaches (Lakens, 2013).

Point estimate refers to the process of estimating an approximate value for a population parameter, such as the mean or average, based on random samples drawn from that population (Encyclopædia Britannica, 2022).

4. RESULTS

Sections of the results:

- 4.1 Characteristics of the study sample.
- 4.2 Obese patients' preferences for the surgery attributes (the whole sample).
- 4.3 Attributes' importance for the whole sample.
- 4.4 Characteristics of risk averse & risk taker groups and the risk of being a risk taker.
- 4.5 Comparison of attributes' importance between risk averse and risk taker groups.
- 4.6 Comparison of attributes levels' utilities between risk averse and risk taker groups.

4.1. Sample characteristics

During six months, a total of 299 obese were surveyed. The majority of patients were between 30 and < 45 years old (56.9%), 75.6% were female, and 75.6% had at least a university education. One third (34.8%) were full-time employees. Approximately, half were just meeting daily expenses (53.2%), 84% were non – smoker, and 65.6% were married. BMIs were between 30-40 in 52.2%. The most frequent health condition was arthritis (21%) (Table 4.1).

Table 4.1: Characteristics of obese candidates for bariatric surgery in MRI bariatric surgery clinic, Alexandria 2022.

Characteristics	n	%
Age group		
18 - <30	84	28.1
30 - <45	170	56.9
45 - <60	40	13.4
60 and above	5	1.7
Gender		
Male	73	24.4
Female	226	75.6
Employment status		
Full time	104	34.8
Student	26	8.7
Retired	5	1.7
Part time	37	12.4
Not working	25	8.4
Homemaker	102	34.1
Marital status		
Married	196	65.6
Unmarried	103	34.4
Smoking		
Yes	47	15.7
No	252	84.3
Household income		
Not meet routine expenses	21	7
Just meet routine expenses	159	53.2
Meet routine expenses and emergencies	95	31.8
Able to save/invest money	24	8
Educational level		
Middle education	68	22.7
University education or above	226	75.6
Uneducated	5	1.7
BMI		
30-40	246	82.3
above 40	53	17.7
Health condition		
Diabetes	29	9.7
Arthritis	64	21.4
Asthma	14	4.7
Hypertension	37	12.4
Hypothyroidism	32	10.7
Sleep apnea	37	12.4
High cholesterol level	32	10.7
None of these	159	53.2

4.2 Obese patients' preferences for the surgery attributes (the whole sample).

For the total sample, the surgical profile has higher preference if it decreases the hunger sensation along with eating a small portion of normal food and buy vitamins, takes 2 weeks recovery but not reversible, 10 years since the surgery was available, resolve all medical conditions with neither risk of complication nor adverse effects and achieve the highest percentage of excess weight loss without any regain (Lose 80%, regain 0%) and has a reasonable cost as shown in [Table 4.2, Figure 4.1].

Table 4.2: Average utility for attributes' levels of bariatric surgery obese in bariatric surgery clinic Medical Research Institute, Alexandria 2022 among

Attributes	Average utility	95%CI
Surgery mechanism of action		
Restrict food/decrease hunger	24.44	(20.84, 28.04)
Restrict food/decrease hunger/restrict absorption	8.43	(4.33, 12.52)
Decrease calories/increase exercise	-8.06	(-11.7, -4.42)
Restrict food/may not decrease hunger	-24.81	(-28.19, -21.43)
Surgery magnitude		
2-wk recovery/not reversible	24.66	(20.23, 29.09)
4-wk recovery/rarely reversible	4.58	(0.78, 8.38)
1-wk recovery/reversible	0.69	(-3.3, 4.69)
No recovery/reversible	-29.94	(-32.57, -27.3)
Surgery availability		
10 years	13.57	(9.47, 17.68)
20 years	0.73	(-3.53, 4.98)
5 years	-0.23	(-5.07, 4.6)
1 year	-14.07	(-19.16, -8.99)
Excess weight loss		
Lose 80%, regain 0%, total loss 80%	28.04	(23.07, 33.01)
Lose 40%, regain 0%, total loss 40%	22.79	(18.26, 27.31)
Lose 80%, regain 20%, total loss 60%	-25.33	(-30.22, -20.44)
Lose 40%, regain 20%, total loss 20%	-25.50	(-31.86, -19.13)
Improvement of health condition		
No HBP/no apnea/no diabetes/no HC	39.24	(35.3, 43.18)
No HBP/no apnea/diabetes/no HC	0.24	(-2.05, 2.52)
No change in any medical condition	-16.87	(-19.4, -14.34)
HBP/apnea/no diabetes/no HC	-22.61	(-25.66, -19.55)
Risk of complication		
0%	34.26	(27.96, 40.57)
5%	29.10	(24.99, 33.21)
20%	-23.28	(-28.03, -18.54)
35%	-40.08	(-44.45, -35.71)
Adverse effect		
No adverse effects	21.63	(15.75, 27.51)
Nausea/vomiting/acid reflux/stomach pains	4.63	(1.6, 7.66)
Malabsorption/possible hair and bone loss	-11.01	(-16.36, -5.65)
Dumping syndrome/diarrhea	-15.25	(-18.95, -11.55)
Diet change		
Normal food with small portions/buy vitamins	29.97	(26.88, 33.06)
Avoid high fat and sugar levels/buy supplements	1.85	(-2.69, 6.4)
No restrictions	-14.44	(-19.12, -9.74)
Calorie restriction/buy specific foods	-17.39	(-19.82, -14.96)
Out of pocket cost		
EGP 50000	10.72	(7.27, 14.16)
EGP 35000	7.28	(2.31, 12.25)
EGP 65000	-18.00	(-21.54, -14.45)

Note: utility values are arranged in descending order + value indicates more preference while - indicates less preference.

HBP: High Blood Pressure.

HC: High Cholesterol.

Figure (4.1): The average utility of attributes' levels for the total sample.

4.3 Attributes' importance for the whole sample.

Attribute's importance was in the following order: the " number of kgs lost in the first year and regained in the second year" (14.67%), the " risk of complication" (13.74%), the presence of "Adverse effects" (11.32%), the "Surgery availability" (11.16%), the "Surgery magnitude" (10.60%), the "Diet changes" (10.41%), the "Surgery mechanism" (10.24%), "improvement of the health condition" (9.33%), and the "out of pocket cost" (8.52%).

Table 4.3: Patients' perceptions of the importance of bariatric surgery attributes

Attribute	Importance	Lower 95% CI	Upper 95% CI
Excess weight loss	14.67	14.10	15.23
Risk of complication	13.74	13.03	14.45
Adverse effects	11.32	10.73	11.91
Surgery availability	11.16	10.69	11.64
Surgery magnitude	10.60	10.20	11.00
Diet changes	10.41	9.95	10.88
Surgery mechanism	10.24	9.91	10.58
Improvement of health condition	9.33	8.82	9.84
Out of pocket cost	8.52	7.97	9.07

Figure (4.2): Bariatric Surgery attributes' relative importance by obese candidate attending bariatric surgery clinic in MRI, Alexandria 2022.

4.4 Characteristics of risk averse & risk taker groups and the risk of being a risk taker.

K-Means analysis using a novel meta-clustering algorithm and based on utility values of levels and demographic criteria revealed two primary clusters with reproducibility 98.7%, where risk taker cluster holding the majority of analysed cases (56%) compared to the risk averse cluster (44%). Regarding demographic characteristics, we found no significant difference between risk averse & risk takers apart from age & education level. Those ages between 45 and 60 years old were more likely to be risk takers compared to those ages 18 - < 30 years old (OR= 2.21, CI (1.03, 4.75)). Also, those whose education was less than university were more likely to be risk takers compared to university education or higher (OR= 1.87, CI (1.07,3.25)) as shown in Table 4.4

Table 4.4: Characteristics of risk averse and risk taker and risks for being a risk taker.

Characteristics	Risk averse (132)	Risk taker (167)	X ²	P value	OR	Lower CI	Upper CI
Age group							
18 - < 30	42(31.8 %)	42(25.1 %)				Reference	
30 - < 40	76(57.6%)	94(56.3%)	4.29	.117	1.24	0.73	2.09
45-60	14(10.6%)	31(18.6%)			2.21*	1.03	4.75
Gender							
Female	102(77.3%)	124(74.3%)				Reference	
Male	30(22.70%)	43(25.7%)	.365	.546	1.18	0.69	2.01
Employment status							
Employed	64(48.5%)	77(46.1%)				Reference	
Unemployed	68(51.5%)	90(53.9%)	.167	.683	1.1	0.70	1.74
Marital status							
Married	81(61.4%)	115(68.9%)				Reference	
Unmarried	51(38.6%)	52(31.1%)	1.836	.175	0.72	0.44	1.16
Smoking							
No	113(85.6 %)	139(83.2 %)				Reference	
Yes	19(14.4 %)	28(16.8 %)	.313	.576	1.20	0.64	2.26
Household income							
Not meet or just meet routine expenses	83(62.9%)	97(58.1%)				Reference	
Meet routine expenses or saving	49(37.1%)	70(41.9%)	.707	.400	1.22	0.77	1.95
Educational level							
University education or above	108(81.8%)	118(70.7%)				Reference	
Less than a university education	24(18.2%)	49(29.3%)	4.975	.026*	1.87*	1.07	3.25
BMI							
Above 40	27(20.5 %)	26(15.6 %)				Reference	
Below 40	105(79.5%)	141(84.4 %)	1.207	.272	1.39	0.77	2.53
Comorbidity							
No	76(57.6%)	83(49.7%)				Reference	
Yes	56(42.4%)	84(50.3%)	1.836	.175	1.37	0.086600	2.18

OR: Simple logistic regression

*: statistically significant (p<0.05)

4.5 Comparison of attributes' importance between risk averse and risk taker groups.

For risk averse attributes' importance were in the following order, "Risk of complication" (19.12), "adverse effect" (12.95), "Excess weight loss" (12.81), "Improvement of health condition" (10.09), "Surgery magnitude" (9.93), "surgery availability " (9.29), "Diet change" (8.47), and "out of pocket cost" (7.05) (Table 4.5, Figure 4.3).

Whereas for risk takers attributes' importance were in the following order, "excess weight loss" (16.13), "surgery availability" (12.65), "Diet change" (11.95), "surgery magnitude" (11.13), "adverse effect" (10.03), "out of pocket cost" (9.67), "Risk of complication" (9.49), and "Improvement of health condition" (8.73).

Table 4.5: Comparison of attributes' importance between clusters risk averse and risk taker

Characteristics	Risk averse (132)		Risk taker (167)		Cohen's d		Statistical test	
	Mean	± SD	Mean	± SD	Est.	95%CI	t	Sig. (2-tailed)
Surgery mechanism of action	10.28	2.88	10.21	3.08	0.02	(-0.20,0.25)	0.21	0.837
Surgery magnitude	9.93	3.36	11.13	3.57	-0.35	(-0.57, -0.11)	-2.96	0.003*
Surgery availability	9.29	3.77	12.65	3.96	-0.87	(-1.1, -0.63)	-7.44	0.001*
Excess weight loss	12.81	4.41	16.13	4.91	-0.71	(-0.94, -0.47)	-6.08	0.001*
Improvement of health condition	10.09	4.80	8.73	4.16	0.31	(0.08, 0.53)	2.62	0.009 *
Risk of complication	19.12	4.47	9.49	3.73	2.36	(2.07, 2.66)	19.88	0.001*
Adverse effect	12.95	5.46	10.03	4.59	0.59	(0.35, 0.82)	4.92	0.001*
Diet change	8.47	3.38	11.95	4.02	-0.93	(-1.17, -0.69)	-7.96	0.001*
Out of pocket cost	7.05	3.94	9.67	5.19	-0.56	(-0.79, -0.33)	-4.97	0.001*

t: Independent t-test

*: statistically significant

Figure (4.3): Comparison between attributes' importance between clusters risk averse and risk taker.

4.6 Comparison of attributes levels' utilities between risk averse and risk taker groups.

Risk averse preferred a surgical profile similar to risk takers apart from complications, adverse effects, and cost. They preferred a surgical profile free from complications as well as adverse effects and with low cost. (Table 4.6 Figure 4.4)

Risk taker preferred a surgical profile that restricts food with decreasing hunger allowing eating small portions of mammal food with a vitamin supplement, irreversible with 2 weeks recovery, available since 10 years, causing 80% weight loss without any regain, improving existing medical conditions, with 5% risk of complications, nausea vomiting reflex stomach pain as adverse effects and with medium cost.

Table 4.6: Comparison of average utilities of attributes' levels between risk averse and risk taker.

Characteristics	Risk averse N:132		Risk taker N:167		t	Sig. (2-tailed)	Point estimate	95% CI
	Average utility	SD	Average utility	SD				
Surgery mechanism of action								
Restrict food/may not decrease hunger	-31.52	25.7	-19.51	31.58	-3.61	0.001	-0.41	(-0.64, -0.18)
Decrease calories/increase exercise	-13.94	27.3	-3.41	34.72	-2.93	0.004	-0.33	(-0.56, -0.1)
Restrict food/decrease hunger	34.35	28.49	16.61	31.97	4.98	0.001	0.58	(0.35, 0.81)
Restrict food/decrease hunger/restrict absorption	11.12	31.62	6.30	39.10	1.17	0.241	0.13	(-0.1, 0.36)
Surgery magnitude								
No recovery/reversible	-23.93	21.40	-34.68	23.53	4.07	0.001	0.47	(0.24, 0.7)
1-wk recovery/reversible	-7.57	29.56	7.22	37.78	-3.79	0.001	-0.43	(-0.66, -0.2)
2-wk recovery/not reversible	32.41	35.77	18.54	40.30	3.09	0.002	0.36	(0.13, 0.59)
4-wk recovery/rarely reversible	-0.91	31.04	8.92	34.70	-2.54	0.012	-0.30	(-0.52, -0.07)
Surgery availability								
1 year	-19.55	34.40	-9.75	51.15	-1.97	0.050	-0.22	(-0.45, 0.01)
5 years	0.58	37.27	-0.86	46.47	0.30	0.766	0.03	(-0.19, 0.26)
10 years	12.29	27.38	14.59	41.76	-0.57	0.569	-0.06	(-0.29, 0.17)
20 years	6.67	31.5	-3.97	40.98	2.53	0.012	0.29	(0.06, 0.52)
Excess weight loss								
Lose 80%, regain 20%, total loss 60%	-17.7	35.39	-31.36	47.37	2.84	0.005	0.32	(0.09, 0.55)
Lose 40%, regain 20%, total loss 20%	-32.07	41.64	-20.30	64.76	-1.90	0.059	-0.21	(-0.44, 0.019)
Lose 40%, regain 0%, total loss 40%	23.01	35.71	22.62	42.89	0.09	0.932	0.01	(-0.22, 0.24)
Lose 80%, regain 0%, total loss 80%	26.76	42.23	29.04	44.93	-0.45	0.656	-0.05	(-0.28, 0.18)
Improvement of health condition								
No change in any medical condition	-14.97	21.77	-18.37	22.59	1.31	0.191	0.15	(-0.08, 0.38)
HBP/apnea/no diabetes/no HC	-28.13	29.78	-18.24	23.50	-3.20	0.002	-0.37	(-0.6, -0.14)
No HBP/no apnea/no diabetes/no HC	44.51	34.36	35.08	34.43	2.35	0.020	0.27	(0.04, 0.5)
No HBP/apnea/diabetes/no HC	-1.41	21.1	1.54	19.26	-1.26	0.209	-0.15	(-0.37, 0.08)
Risk of complication								
35%	-61.65	33.62	-23.04	33.17	8.50	0.001	1.04	(0.8, 1.28)
0%	62.98	60.02	11.56	38.86	6.87	0.001	0.84	(0.6, 1.08)
5%	44.8	40.58	16.69	26.34	-9.21	0.001	-1.12	(-1.36, -0.87)
20%	-46.13	43.17	-5.22	30.24	-9.90	0.001	-1.15	(-1.4, -0.91)
Adverse effect								
Dumping syndrome/diarrhea	-26.25	31.54	-6.56	30.80	-5.41	0.001	-0.63	(-0.86, -0.4)
No adverse effects	45.80	47.52	2.52	46.79	7.86	0.001	0.92	(0.68, 1.15)
Nausea/vomiting/acid reflux/stomach pains	-2.41	26.54	10.20	25.41	-4.16	0.001	-0.48	(-0.72, -0.25)
Malabsorption/possible hair and bone loss	-17.14	49.42	-6.16	44.78	-1.98	0.049	-0.23	(-0.46, -0.004)
Diet change								
Calorie restriction/buy specific foods	-9.29	17.59	-23.80	21.92	6.33	0.001	0.72	(0.48, 0.95)
Normal food with small portions/buy vitamins	23.69	21.26	34.94	30.20	-3.76	0.001	-0.42	(-0.65, -0.19)
No restrictions	-12.35	34.99	-16.08	45.59	0.80	0.426	0.09	(-0.14, 0.32)
Avoid high fat and sugar levels/buy supplements	-2.05	33.3	4.94	44.40	-1.55	0.122	-0.17	(-0.4, 0.05)
Out of pocket cost								
EGP 35000	12.74	34.47	2.97	49.53	2.00	0.046	0.22	(-0.005, 0.45)
EGP 50000	1.15	27.38	18.27	30.47	-5.03	0.001	-0.59	(-0.82, -0.35)
EGP 65000	-13.9	25.94	-21.24	34.51	2.09	0.037	0.24	(0.006, 0.46)

Figure (4.4): Comparison between risk averse and risk taker in the mean utility values.

DISCUSSION

We divided this chapter into six sections:

- 5.1 Appropriateness of adaptive choice based conjoint analysis (ACBC) experiment to answer the research questions.
- 5.2 Total obese patients' preferences for bariatric surgery
- 5.3 Risk perception of bariatric surgery on obese patients
- 5.4 Strengths
- 5.5 Limitations

5.1 Appropriateness of adaptive choice based conjoint analysis (ACBC) experiment to answer the research questions.

When deciding what healthcare interventions and services to prioritize, certain nations, including the UK, now routinely consider the opinions of residents and communities. Decision policies should make a valuable contribution to the shared decision-making by giving patients and clinicians a structure that enables them to integrate their values and beliefs to recognize the best outcome and favor the alternative that gets patients close to the goal they defined with the clinician's support. Public engagement in the healthcare decision-making process allowed policy makers to identify critical points that should be tackled. Patients are the only ones who can recognize relevant elements when making a life-altering choice (Bailo et al., 2019).

In the field of bariatric surgery to identify which surgery attributes are preferred, the adaptive choice based conjoint analysis seems to be the best method to achieve this purpose for the reasons: It is one of the most advanced and tailored applications that learn from respondents when answering different types of questions in multiple stages (build your own stage, screening stage and choice tournament stage), also it can probe deeper into each respondent's choice hierarchy and have both solid behavioral (consideration, then choice) and statistical theory (near-orthogonal experiments and choice data) which make it the ideal tool for achievement the goal (Orme, 2014).

Moreover, this method has been widely used to identify patients' preferences in different health care disciplines such as pharmacological chronic pain treatment (Smith et al., 2016), biological medicines for Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) (Almario et al., 2018), hospital characteristics (de Groot et al., 2011), and palliative treatment in the advanced stages of breast cancer (Reinisch et al., 2021).

5.2 Preference of obese patients for bariatric surgery.

Results from our study suggesting that the most preferred bariatric procedure among obese patients was the permanent procedure such as sleeve gastrectomy utility value of 24.66 (95% CI: 20.84 - 28.04) which was similar to another research reported that sleeve gastrectomy followed by gastric bypass, vertical banded gastroplasty, and gastric banding (Lee et al., 2005).

Several studies addressed different explanations behind the highest preference for sleeve gastrectomy such as achieving the greatest amount of weight loss (Mahfouz et al., 2021), improvement of comorbidity (Roh et al., 2020) with lower readmissions and less cost relative to other procedures (Kizy et al., 2017).

The second preferable surgery in our study was surgeries that are reversible in rare cases 4.58 (95% CI: 0.78- 8.38) as gastric bypass followed by the reversible options - 29.94(95% CI: -32.57- -27.3) like gastric banding as it causes a significant decrease in preferences for sweet foods which may contribute to weight loss (Redpath et al., 2018).

However, another study found that the most preferred surgery was laparoscopic adjustable gastric banding (LAGB) due to its safety and least invasiveness (Ren et al., 2005). Apovian et al. (2013) study revealed that patients' preference for gastric banding rather than gastric bypass. They claimed that factors such as patients' diabetic status, quality of life, eating habits, desired weight reduction, and willingness to accept mortality risk were highly affecting the decision making.

The most important surgery attributes from our obese patients' point of view were the amount of weight loss 14.67(95% CI: 14.10 - 15.23) followed by risk of complication 13.74 (95% CI: 13.03-14.45), then adverse effects 11.32(95% CI: 10.73-11.91). This finding is supported by a study that reported that patients seeking bariatric surgery frequently report desiring the maximum amount of weight loss (Weinstein et al., 2014). Out-of-pocket cost was identified as the least influential attribute, which was in contrast to the findings of a study that observed a decrease in demand for surgery as the cost of the procedure increased, regardless of the presence or absence of comorbidities (Martin et al., 2010).

Focusing on different outcomes rather than weight loss such as solving medical problems and improving quality of life were the most essential factors to consider when seeking bariatric surgery in many studies (Munoz et al., 2007; Fischer et al., 2014; Rahiri et al., 2019). In Saudi Arabia, other important outcomes considered beside improvement of the medical condition were less negative side effects, and short recovery period after the surgery (Mahfouz et al., 2021).

However, distinct point of view was addressed in other studies such as safety and invasiveness which had the greatest impact on patient choice (Ren et al., 2005). Also, the risk of complications was more considered over the amount of weight loss (Murtha et al., 2022), the reoperation rate (Lam et al., 2022), the recovery time, and the duration of benefits from a diabetic obese perspective to consider bariatric surgery as a possible way of cure (Chua et al., 2016). From the perspective of obese African American women risk of complications, amount of weight loss, and physical lifestyle restrictions, are the most critical elements that determine their preference for bariatric surgery (Lynch et al., 2007).

Through the importance of the amount of weight lost, it is evident that the preferences vary across different studies. This could be attributed to the perception of the individuals, their current health status, and their quality of life. It differs from what mostly bother them.

5.3. Risk perception of bariatric surgery among obese patients

To understand the obese patient preference in the decision making process and explain it more clearly, we carried out a k-mean clustering analysis which perfectly divided our obese patients into risk averse (44%) and risk taker (56%). They differed in the most important desirable outcome as the risk averse group mainly focuses on the risk of complications (19.12) while the risk taker group trading off any type of risk to achieve the largest amount of weight loss (16.13). Being male or female doesn't affect the likelihood of being a risk taker or risk averse. However, the older age (between 45 and 60) and the lower level of education increased the likelihood to accept the risk of complications (being a risk taker).

The risk of undergoing bariatric surgery is perceived differently by various groups of obese patients as males at advanced stages of comorbidities were more likely to perceive the risk of heart disease and death from surgical complications (Chang et al., 2014; Lee et al., 2015; Schakarowski et al., 2018), in contrast to females who were more focusing on the social and beauty standards, so they were seeking the bariatric surgery at less advanced stages of the disease (Steffen et al., 2012; Pona et al., 2016).

A study on obese patients suffering from type 2 diabetes revealed that they were willing to accept the risk of bariatric surgery as their disease is called a silent killer and can result in a series of consequences (Schakarowski, 2018). However, our results identified that the health condition of an obese patient doesn't increase the likelihood to accept the risk of complications and justify being a risk taker.

5.4. Strengths

- It is the first study in Egypt that used adaptive choice based conjoint analysis (ACBC) to identify patient preference. ACBC is superior to standard choice based conjoint analysis (CBC).
- The use of a novel technique which is the Adaptive choice based conjoint analysis to measure patients' preferences and determine the motivation behind their choices allowing choices to be tailored depending on the patient's answers in each step.
- We also performed a segmented utility analysis and simulation scenarios which were only conducted by this unique method to provide individualized patients' preferences.
- The Sawtooth program which we used to develop the questionnaire relies on artificial intelligence technology to better develop the appeared choices in each step depending on the personalized preference to determine which options are must have or unacceptable for them so for each time the questionnaire is redesigned individually which make it more interactive for the respondents (Sawtooth Software, 2021).
- We are one of the few researches that used conjoint analysis to determine both the percentage of importance of attributes and part worth utility of levels. Other comparable studies used discrete choice conjoint analysis (DCE) for the same purpose but had limitations regarding the complexity of the analysis as DCE only permitted a small number of attributes to be valid. This was resolved by our method which integrated a large number of attributes in different stages to determine the final preferred choice set (Roziar et al., 2019).

5.5. Limitations

- The Survey required a long time to be completed (about 15 minutes) which put a cognitive burden on patients but this is due to the ability of ACBC to collect more information on the individual level with a smaller sample size and simulate the real process of decision making.
- Small sample size from a single region. However, with the ACBC technique, this sample size is often sufficient for eliciting patients' preferences.

6. SUMMARY, RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION

6. 1 Summary

6.1.1. Introduction

Bariatric surgery shared decision-making, which integrates patient values and preferences with current medical knowledge to aid in the challenging selection process for bariatric surgery and help the public system allocate resources, may be beneficial to both patients and practitioners.

If surgeons were asked to assume the role of their patients, their preferences would be comparable to those of the patients, with some exceptions, notably those relating to sensitivity to the risk of consequences and out-of- pocket expenses. Most of the research on bariatric surgery patients studied the public knowledge, perceptions, and acceptability of different types and features related to the surgery.

We found few studies that focused on the preferences of patient populations weather suffering from certain medical conditions like diabetes or other medical conditions beside obesity or focusing on certain patient category like those comparing males and females' preferences.

This study aims to reveal the full picture and the whole case scenario of the Egyptian obese patient's preference for bariatric surgery using a novel technique adaptive choice based conjoint analysis (ACBC).

6.1.2. Methods

Study design: A cross-sectional survey was conducted during which the adaptive choice based tasks were presented to the patients.

Setting: The bariatric surgery clinic of the Medical Research Institute, Alexandria University.

Population: Patients seeking weight loss at the bariatric surgery clinic of the Medical Research Institute, Alexandria University.

Sample size: The minimum required sample size is 250 respondents. It was calculated and tested using Sawtooth software which is computer software specialized in conjoint analysis and provides tools that help in creating, fielding, and analyzing market research surveys.

Adaptive choice based conjoint analysis survey which created using sawtooth software was consisted of four parts:

- A sociodemographic survey collected the participants' age, sex, marital status, educational level, employment status, medical conditions, current BMI, and income.
- ACBC tasks that changed based on the response given by the participant explored their perceptions the importance of different features in bariatric surgery in the decision making process and explore the trade off process that occur during their choices, which consist of three stages:
 - Build your own (BYO) configuration section, where only one level is indicated by patients as the most preferred one per each attribute.
 - Screening section, which used an alternative specific design that generated distinct sets of attributes and identify must have and unacceptable options for each alternative based on the artificial intelligence technology.
 - Choice tasks section which utilize the partial specific design that focused on a limited number of traits beside that the number of choice tasks varies between respondents based on the respondents' determination and selection of levels of particular attributes until determining the most preferred choice set based on a trade off process in different generated scenarios.

6.1.3 Statistical Analyses:

- **Adaptive Choice based Conjoint Analysis:** Sawtooth software was used to determine the relative importance for each attribute as well as the part worth utility for their levels using a hierarchical Bayes (HB) analysis model.
- **Clustering analyses:** K-mean clustering analysis based on utility values of levels and demographic criteria which divided the data into two groups (Risk averse VS Risk taker).
- **Comparison analysis between the clusters (Risk averse VS Risk taker):** Comparative analysis based on both sociodemographic characteristics as well as the values of attribute importance and level's utility values.

6.1.4 Results

During six months, a total of 299 obese were surveyed. The majority of patients were between 30 and < 45 years old (56.9%), 75.6% were female, and 75.6% had at least a university education. One third (34.8%) were full-time employees. Approximately, half were just meeting daily expenses (53.2%), 84% were non – smoker, 65.6% were married, and BMIs were between 30-40 in 52.2%. The most frequent health condition was arthritis (21%).

For the total sample, the surgical profile has a higher preference if it decreases the hunger sensation along with eating a small portion of normal food and buy vitamins not reversible with 10 years availability, resolve all medical conditions with neither risk of complication nor adverse effects and achieve the highest percentage of excess weight loss without any regain (Lose 80%, regain 0%) with reasonable cost.

Attribute's importance were in the following order: " number of kgs lost in the first year and regained in the second year" (14.67%), "risk of complication" (13.74%), "Adverse effects" (11.32%), "Surgery availability" (11.16%), "Surgery magnitude" (10.60%), "Diet changes" (10.41%), "Surgery mechanism" (10.24%), "improvement of health condition" (9.33%), and "out of pocket cost" (8.52%).

K-Means analysis using a novel meta-clustering algorithm and based on utility values of levels and demographic criteria revealed two primary clusters with reproducibility 98.7%, where risk taker cluster holding the most of analysed cases (56%) compared to risk averse cluster (44%). Regarding demographic characteristics, we found no significant difference between risk averse & risk taker except for education level. Those whose ages between 45 and 60 years old were more likely to be risk taker compared to ages 18 - < 30 years old (OR= 2.21, CI (1.03, 4.75)). Also, those whose education was less than university were more likely to be risk taker compared to university education or higher (OR= 1.87, CI (1.07,3.25)).

For risk takers attributes' importance were in the following order, "excess weight loss" (16.13), "surgery availability" (12.65), "Diet change" (11.95), "surgery magnitude" (11.13), "surgery mechanism of action" (10.21), "adverse effect" (10.03), "out of pocket cost" (9.67), "Risk of complication" (9.49), and "Improvement of health condition" (8.73).

Whereas for risk averse attributes' importance were in the following order, "Risk of complication" (19.12), "adverse effect" (12.95), "Excess weight loss" (12.81), "Surgery mechanism of action" (10.28), "Improvement of health condition" (10.09), "Surgery magnitude" (9.93), "surgery availability " (9.29), "Diet change" (8.47), and "out of pocket cost" (7.05).

Risk taker preferred a surgical profile that restricts food with decreasing hunger allowing eating small portions from mammal food with a vitamin supplement, irreversible with 2 weeks recovery, available since 10 years, causing 80% weight loss without any regain, improving existing medical conditions, with 5% risk of complications, nausea vomiting reflex stomach pain as adverse effects and with medium cost.

Risk averse preferred a surgical profile similar to risk takers except for complications, adverse effects, and cost. They preferred a surgical profile free from complications as well as adverse effects and with low cost.

6.1.5 Conclusion

The most preferable bariatric surgical profile for obese patients was that which decreases the hunger sensation along with eating small portions of normal food and buy vitamins, resolve all medical conditions with neither risk of complication nor adverse effects, and achieve the highest percentage of excess weight without any regain (Lose 80%, regain 0%) and with reasonable cost.

After conducting cluster analysis our sample was divided into risk taker group which focused on weight loss regardless of the risk of complications they may face in the surgery. On the other hand, the risk averse group was more considering the risk of complication as a critical point when choosing the surgical profile. Out of pocket cost was more important for the risk taker group.

6.1.6 Recommendations

- Assessing and integrating patient preference with the surgeon's experience to make the ideal decision.
- Keeping a database for patients' preferences and utilizing this information along with the patient profile to decide whether or not performing the bariatric surgery.
- Using the adaptive choice based conjoint analysis experiment as a valuable tool in identifying patients' preferences studies regarding different sectors and services in health care.
- Emphasizing positive weight loss impact and cost-effectiveness for risk takers to help them in making informed decisions that align with their priorities .
- Focusing on safety, durability, and long-term health benefits for the risk-averse group, addressing potential complications with reassurance to guide them in the decision making process.

A conceptual framework for the attributes and levels is shown below.

- How the surgery will help you to lose weight attribute including 4 levels:

- 1) Reduce calories, increase exercise, behavior modification.

- 2) Restrict the amount of food that can be eaten at one time but may not decrease feelings of hunger.

- 3) Restricts the amount of food that can be eaten at one time and decreases feelings of hunger.

- 4) Restricts the amount of food that can be eaten at one time, decreases feelings of hunger, and restricts absorption of nutrients from food.

- Surgery magnitude: the amount of recovery time needed to be based on the reversibility of the surgical procedure including four levels.

- 1) No recovery is needed; the procedure is reversible.

- 2) You will need one week to recover from the procedure, the procedure is reversible.

- 3) You will need two weeks to recover from the procedure, the procedure is permanent.

- 4) You will need four weeks to recover from the procedure, the procedure is reversible in rare cases.

- Surgery availability (number of years since the surgery has been available) including 4 levels.

- 1) 1 year

- 2) 5 years

- 3) 10 years

- 4) 20 years

•Number of kilograms you prefer to lose in year 1 and the regained percentage of them in year 2, including 4 levels.

1) You are expected to lose [40% excess body weight] Kgs in year 1 and regain [20% excess body weight] Kgs in year 2.

2) You are expected to lose [40% excess body weight] Kgs in year 1 and regain [0% excess body weight] Kgs in year 2.

3) You are expected to lose [80% excess body weight] Kgs in year 1 and regain [20% excess body weight] Kgs in year 2.

4) You are expected to lose [80% excess body weight] Kgs in year 1 and regain [0% excess body weight] Kgs in year 2.

•Improvement of weight associated medical conditions: number of other weight-related medical conditions that are no longer a problem after you start treatment. These conditions include prediabetes, diabetes, high blood pressure, high cholesterol, and sleep apnea, including four levels.

1) No change, you still have diabetes, high cholesterol, high blood pressure, and sleep apnea.

2) You still have high blood pressure and sleep apnea, but you no longer have diabetes and high cholesterol.

3) You still have diabetes, but you no longer have sleep apnea, high blood pressure, or high cholesterol.

4) You no longer have diabetes, high blood pressure, high cholesterol, and sleep apnea.

•Risk of complication within 3 years attribute: percent of individuals that are expected to experience a complication within 3 years of the treatment. Examples of complications include internal bleeding, leaking, infection, and blood clots directly after the procedure or treatment. Later complications could include problems like ulcers, bowel obstructions, hernia, kidney stones, and gallbladder removal, including four levels.

1) 0%

2) 5%

3) 20%

4) 35%

•Side effects attribute common negative side effects that may result from the treatment. These side effects may be present for the rest of your life after treatment, including four levels.

1) None

2) Nausea, vomiting, difficulty swallowing, acid reflux, stomach pains, intolerance to certain foods.

3) Dumping syndrome, loose stools, and diarrhea

4) Malabsorption and nutrient deficiencies which can result in bone loss, hair loss, etc.

•Diet changes attribute: there are special diets that must be followed the treatment to maintain weight loss over the long term. After a procedure, the diet is considered a permanent lifestyle change, including four levels.

1) No restrictions.

2) Calories are significantly restricted each day and you must purchase special food products

3) You can eat normal foods in smaller portions to avoid side effects, but you must also purchase vitamins the rest of your life

4) You must avoid foods high in sugar and fat to avoid side effects. You must also purchase supplements like protein shakes and vitamins for the rest of your life.

•Initial out of pocket cost attribute: amount of out-of-pocket costs associated with the treatment and follow-up care in the first year following treatment including three levels.

1) 35000

2) 50000

3) 65000

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الملخص العربي

جراحة السمنة قد يكون اتخاذ القرار المشترك ، الذي يدمج قيم المريض وتفضيلاته مع المعرفة الطبية الحالية للمساعدة في عملية الاختيار الصعبة لجراحة السمنة ومساعدة النظام العام على تخصيص الموارد ، مفيدا لكل من المرضى والممارسين.

إذا طلب من الجراحين تولي دور مرضاهم ، فإن تفضيلاتهم ستكون مماثلة لتفضيلات المرضى ، مع بعض الاستثناءات ، لا سيما تلك المتعلقة بالحساسية لمخاطر العواقب والنفقات من الجيب. درست معظم الأبحاث التي أجريت على مرضى جراحة السمنة المعرفة العامة والتصورات ومقبولية الأنواع والميزات المختلفة المتعلقة بالجراحة.

وجدنا عددا قليلا من الدراسات التي ركزت على تفضيلات المرضى الذين يعانون من حالة طبية معينة مثل مرض السكري أو حالات طبية أخرى بجانب السمنة أو التركيز على فئة معينة من المرضى مثل تلك التي تقارن تفضيل الذكور والإناث.

تهدف هذه الدراسة إلى الكشف عن الصورة الكاملة وسيناريو الحالة الكاملة لتفضيل مرضى السمنة المصريين لجراحة السمنة باستخدام تقنية جديدة للتحليل المشترك القائم على الاختيار التكيفي (ACBC).

طريقة البحث

تصميم الدراسة: مسح مقطعي يتم إجراؤه خلاله المهام القائمة على الاختيار التكيفي المقدمة للمرضى.

المكان: عيادة جراحة السمنة بمعهد البحوث الطبية جامعة الإسكندرية.

الفئة المستهدفة: المرضى الذين يسعون لفقدان الوزن في عيادة جراحة السمنة بمعهد البحوث الطبية بجامعة الإسكندرية.

حجم العينة: الحد الأدنى لحجم العينة المطلوب هو 250 مستجيبا. تم حسابه واختباره باستخدام برنامج Sawtooth وهو برنامج كمبيوتر متخصص في التحليل الموحد ويوفر أدوات تساعد في إنشاء استطلاعات الأبحاث الاقتصادية ونشرها وتحليلها.

تألف مسح التحليل المشترك القائم على الاختيار التكيفي والذي تم إنشاؤه باستخدام برنامج Sawtooth من أربعة أجزاء:

- جمع مسح اجتماعي ديموغرافي عمر المشاركين وجنسهم وحالتهم الاجتماعية ومستواهم التعليمي وحالة التوظيف والظروف الطبية ومؤشر كتلة الجسم الحالي والدخل.

• استكشفت مهام (ACBC) التي تغيرت بناء على الاستجابة التي قدمها المشاركون تصوراتهم حول أهمية الميزات المختلفة في جراحة السمنة في عملية صنع القرار واستكشاف عملية المفاضلة التي تحدث أثناء اختياراتهم ، والتي تتكون من ثلاث مراحل:

- حيث يشير المرضى إلى مستوى واحد فقط باعتباره المستوى الأكثر تفضيلاً لكل سمة.
- قم ببناء قسم التكوين الخاص بك (BYO): قسم الفرز الذي استخدم تصميمًا محددًا بديلًا أنتج مجموعات متميزة من السمات وتحديد الخيارات التي يجب أن تتوفر وغير مقبولة لكل بديل بناءً على تقنية الذكاء الاصطناعي.
- قسم مهام الاختيار الذي يستخدم التصميم المحدد الجزئي الذي ركز على عدد محدود من السمات إلى جانب أن عدد مهام الاختيار يختلف بين المستجيبين بناءً على تحديد المستجيبين واختيار مستويات سمات معينة حتى إلغاء مجموعة الاختيار الأكثر تفضيلاً بناءً على عملية المفاضلة في سيناريوهات مختلفة تم إنشاؤها.

التحليلات الإحصائية:

التحليل المشترك القائم على الاختيار التكيفي: لتحديد الأهمية النسبية لكل سمة تم استخدام برنامج Sawtooth بالإضافة إلى فائدة الجزء ذي القيمة لمستوياتها باستخدام نموذج تحليل النمذجة التسلسلية لبايز (HB).
تحليلات التجميع: تحليل التجميع لمتوسط استناداً إلى قيم المنفعة للمستويات والمعايير الديموغرافية التي قسمت البيانات إلى مجموعتين (تجنب المخاطر مقابل المخاطرة).
تحليل المقارنة بين المجموعات (تجنب المخاطر مقابل المخاطر): تحليل مقارن يعتمد على كل من الخصائص الاجتماعية الديموغرافية بالإضافة إلى قيم أهمية السمة وقيم المنفعة للمستوى.

النتائج

خلال فترة ثلاثة أشهر ، تم مسح ما مجموعه 299 من مرضى السمنة المفرطة. تراوحت أعمار غالبية المرضى بين 30 و > 45 عاماً (56.9٪) ، و 75.6٪ من الإناث ، و 75.6٪ حصلوا على تعليم جامعي على الأقل. وكان الثلث (34.8٪) موظفين بدوام كامل. تقريباً ، كان نصفهم يستوفون النفقات اليومية فقط (53.2٪) ، و 84٪ غير مدخنين ، و 65.6٪ متزوجون ، وكان مؤشر كتلة الجسم 30-40 في (52.2٪) . كانت الحالة الصحية الأكثر شيوعاً هي التهاب المفاصل (21٪).

بالنسبة للعينة الإجمالية ، يكون للملف الجراحي تفضيل أعلى إذا كان يقلل من الإحساس بالجوع إلى جانب تناول جزء صغير من الطعام العادي وشراء الفيتامينات و تأثير الجراحة دائم بالإضافة لتواجدها منذ 10 سنوات ، وتحسين جميع المشكلات الصحية دون التعرض لخطر المضاعفات أو الآثار الجانبية وتحقيق أعلى نسبة من فقدان الوزن الزائد دون أي استعادة (تفقد 80 ٪ ، استعادة 0٪) بتكلفة معقولة.

كانت أهمية السمات بالترتيب التالي: "عدد الكيلوغرامات المفقودة في السنة الأولى والمستعادة في السنة الثانية" (14.67٪)، "خطر حدوث مضاعفات" (13.74٪)، "الآثار الجانبية" (11.32٪)، "توفر الجراحة" (11.16٪)، "حجم الجراحة" (10.60٪)، "تغييرات النظام الغذائي" (10.41٪)، "آلية الجراحة" (10.24٪)، "تحسين الحالة الصحية" (9.33٪)، و "التكلفة من الجيب" (8.52٪).

كشفت تحليل K-Means باستخدام خوارزمية التجميع التلوي الجديدة واستنادا إلى قيم المنفعة للمستويات والمعايير الديموغرافية عن مجموعتين أساسيتين مع قابلية التكرار بنسبة 98.7٪، حيث تمتلك مجموعة المخاطرة معظم الحالات التي تم تحليلها (56٪) مقارنة بمجموعة تجنب المخاطر (44٪). فيما يتعلق بالخصائص الديموغرافية، لم نجد فرقا كبيرا بين النفور من المخاطرة والمجازفة باستثناء مستوى التعليم. أولئك الذين تتراوح أعمارهم بين 45 و60 عاما كانوا أكثر عرضة للمخاطرة مقارنة بالأعمار من 18 إلى > 30 عاما (OR= 2.21, CI (1.03, 4.75)) كما أن أولئك الذين كان تعليمهم أقل من الجامعة كانوا أكثر عرضة للمخاطرة مقارنة بالتعليم الجامعي أو أعلى (OR= 1.87, CI (1.07,3.25))

بالنسبة للمجازفين، كانت أهمية السمات بالترتيب التالي، "فقدان الوزن الزائد" (16.13)، "توافر الجراحة" (12.65)، "تغيير النظام الغذائي" (11.95)، "حجم الجراحة" (11.13)، "آلية عمل الجراحة" (10.21)، "التأثير السلبي" (10.03)، "التكلفة من (8.73). الجيب" (9.67)، "خطر المضاعفات" (9.49)، و "تحسين الحالة الصحية".

في حين أن أهمية السمات بالنسبة لمتجنبين المخاطر كانت بالترتيب التالي، "خطر حدوث مضاعفات" (19.12)، "تأثير ضار" (12.95)، "فقدان الوزن الزائد" (12.81)، "آلية عمل الجراحة" (10.28)، "تحسين الحالة الصحية" (10.09)، "حجم الجراحة" (9.93). "توافر الجراحة" (9.29)، "تغيير النظام الغذائي" (8.47)، و "التكلفة من الجيب (7.05).

يفضل المجازف ملفا جراحيا يقيد الطعام مع تقليل الجوع مما يسمح بتناول أجزاء صغيرة من طعام الثدييات مع مكملات الفيتامينات، تأثير الجراحة دائم مع 2 أسابيع فترة نقاهة، متاح منذ 10 سنوات، يتسبب في فقدان الوزن بنسبة 80٪ دون أي استعادة، وتحسين الظروف الصحية الحالية، مع خطر حدوث مضاعفات بنسبة 5٪، والغثيان والقيء المنعكس آلام في المعدة كآثار جانبية وبتكلفة متوسطة.

في حين يفضل متجنب المخاطر ملفا جراحيا مشابها للمجازفين باستثناء المضاعفات والآثار الجانبية والتكلفة. لقد فضلوا الملف الجراحي الخالي من المضاعفات وكذلك الآثار الجانبية وبتكلفة منخفضة.

كان الملف الجراحي الأكثر تفضيلا لعلاج البدانة للمرضى الذين يعانون من السمنة المفرطة هو الذي يقلل من الإحساس بالجوع جنبا إلى جنب مع تناول جزء صغير من الطعام العادي وشراء الفيتامينات، وحل جميع الحالات الصحية دون خطر حدوث مضاعفات أو آثار ضارة وتحقيق أعلى نسبة من الوزن الزائد دون أي استعادة (تفقد 80٪، استعادة 0٪) وبتكلفة معقولة.

بعد إجراء التحليل العنقودي ، تم تقسيم عينتنا إلى مجموعة المخاطرة التي ركزت على فقدان الوزن بغض النظر عن خطر المضاعفات التي قد يواجهونها في الجراحة. من ناحية أخرى ، كانت المجموعة التي تتجنب المخاطر أكثر مراعاة لخطر المضاعفات كنقطة حرجة عند اختيار الملف الجراحي. كانت التكلفة من الجيب أكثر أهمية لمجموعة المخاطرة.

التوصيات

- تقييم ودمج تفضيل المريض مع خبرة الجراح من أجل اتخاذ القرار المثالي.
- الاحتفاظ بقاعدة بيانات لتفضيلات المرضى واستخدام هذه المعلومات جنباً إلى جنب مع ملف تعريف المريض من أجل تحديد ما إذا كان سيتم إجراء جراحة السمنة أم لا.
- استخدام تجربة التحليل المشترك القائم على الاختيار التكيفي كأداة قيمة في تحديد دراسات تفضيلات المرضى فيما يتعلق بالقطاعات والخدمات المختلفة في مجال الرعاية الصحية.

المستخلص العربي

الهدف: قياس تفضيلات المرضى الذين يعانون من السمنة المفرطة للمخاطر والفوائد والسمات الأخرى لجراحة السمنة في مجموعة من المرضى المرشحين لجراحة السمنة في الإسكندرية.

المكان: عيادة جراحة السمنة بمعهد البحوث الطبية جامعة الإسكندرية

طريقة البحث: تجربة تحليل مشترك قائمة على الاختيار التكيفي لقياس تفضيل المريض البدين لجراحة السمنة. تم وصف كل ملف جراحي بالسمات التالية: (1) طريقة العلاج ، (2) التعافي والعكس ، (3) سنوات من العلاج المتاح ، (4) فقدان الوزن المتوقع ، (5) التأثير على الحالات الطبية الأخرى ، (6) خطر حدوث مضاعفات ، (7) الآثار الجانبية ، (8) التغييرات في النظام الغذائي ، (9) التكاليف النثرية. أجرى المشاركون 4 أقسام استطلاع عبر الإنترنت: (1) الخصائص الاجتماعية والديموغرافية ، (2) قسم بناء بنفسك ، (3) قسم الفحص ، (4) قسم بطولة الاختيار. تم تجنيد عينة ملائمة من المرضى الذين يسعون إلى إنقاص الوزن من عيادة جراحة السمنة بمعهد البحوث الطبية بجامعة الإسكندرية.

النتائج: من بين 299 مستجيبا (75.6% من النساء؛ 56.9% تتراوح أعمارهم بين 30 و 44 عاما) ، الملامح الجراحية للإجراءات الافتراضية التي تضمنت فقدان وزن أعلى (معامل فقدان 80% من الوزن الزائد واستعادة 0% ، 28.04 [95% CI, 23.07- 33.01] ، انخفاض خطر حدوث مضاعفات معامل 0% خطر حدوث مضاعفات ، 34.26 [95% CI, 27.96- 40.57] ، والآثار الضارة الأقل (معامل عدم وجود آثار ضارة [95% CI, 27.96- 40.57] 34.26) كان من المرجح أن يتم اختيارها. حدد التحليل العنقودي K-mean المجموعتين الفرعيتين التاليتين: مجموعة معالجة المخاطر أكثر قلقا بشأن فقدان الوزن الزائد (قيمة معامل فقدان 80% من الوزن الزائد واستعادة [95% CI, 21.38 - 36.71] 29.04 ، وتوافر الجراحة قيمة المعامل لتوافر 10 سنوات ، [95% CI , 7.46 - 21.71] 14.59 وتغيير النظام الغذائي قيمة المعامل للأغذية العادية مع جزء صغير وشراء الفيتامينات، [95% CI, 29.79 - 40.09] 34.94 ، ومجموعة تجنب المخاطر أكثر قلقا بشأن خطر حدوث مضاعفات 0% خطر حدوث مضاعفات ، [95% CI , 52.74 - 73.22] 62.98 ، التأثير السلبي لقيمة المعامل "لا يوجد تأثير ضار " ، [95% CI, 37.7- 53.91] 45.80 وآلية عمل الجراحة قيمة المعامل لتقييد الطعام وتقليل الجوع، [95% CI, 29.49 - 39.21] 34.35.

خلاصة الدراسة: يعتبر المرشح لجراحة السمنة أن فقدان الوزن دون استعادة ما يلي بخطر حدوث مضاعفات في غضون 3 سنوات والآثار الضارة هي أهم السمات ، في حين أن السمات الأقل أهمية هي الأولوية من الجيب وتحسين الحالة الصحية .

اقرار

أقر أنه لا يوجد أي جزء من هذه الرسالة قد سبق تقديمه لنيل درجة اخري في هذه الجامعة أو أية جامعة أو مؤسسة تعليمية أخرى بمصر او بالخارج وأنها تتوافق مع الميثاق الأخلاقي للبحث العلمي لجامعة الإسكندرية وعلى الأخص الأمانة العلمية.

اسم الطالب: دعاء حسين حسن دويدار

توقيعه:

معهد البحوث الطبية
قسم المعلوماتية الحيوية والاحصاء الطبي

تفضيل مريض السمنة فيما يتعلق بجراحة البدانة: تحليل مشترك قائم على اختيار تكيفي

رسالة علمية مقدمة

ضمن متطلبات درجة الماجستير في
المعلوماتية الحيوية والاحصاء الطبي

مقدمة من

دعاء حسين حسن دويدار

بكالوريوس صيدلة – كلية الصيدلة والتصنيع الدوائى - جامعة فاروس- 2019

2023

معهد البحوث الطبية
قسم المعلوماتية الحيوية والاحصاء الطبي

صفحة الموافقة على الرسالة

تفضيل مريض السمنة فيما يتعلق بجراحة البدانة: تحليل مشترك قائم على

اختيار تكيفي

رسالة مقدمة من

دعاء حسين حسن دويدار

للحصول على درجة الماجستير في المعلوماتية الحيوية والاحصاء الطبي

التوقيع	لجنة الحكم والمناقشة
.....	أ.م.د/ أميمة جابر محمد يس أستاذ مساعد بقسم المعلوماتية الحيوية والاحصاء الطبي معهد البحوث الطبية جامعة الإسكندرية
.....	أ.د/ جيهان محمد شحاته حسن أستاذ بقسم المعلوماتية الحيوية والاحصاء الطبي معهد البحوث الطبية جامعة الإسكندرية
.....	أ.د/ خالد محمد قطري أستاذ بقسم الجراحة العامة كلية الطب جامعة الإسكندرية

تاريخ مناقشة الرسالة: 2023/12/13

معهد البحوث الطبية
قسم المعلوماتية الحيوية والاحصاء الطبي

لجنة الإشراف

اسم الطالب: دعاء حسين حسن دويدار

عنوان الرسالة: تفضيل مريض السمنة فيما يتعلق بجراحة البدانة: تحليل مشترك قائم على اختيار تكيفي

اسم الدرجة: ماجستير المعلوماتية الحيوية والاحصاء الطبي

التوقيع	لجنة الإشراف
.....	أ.م.د/ أميمة جابر محمد يس أستاذ مساعد بقسم المعلوماتية الحيوية والاحصاء الطبي معهد البحوث الطبية جامعة الإسكندرية
.....	أ.م.د/ غادة ابو شعيشع أستاذ مساعد بقسم المعلوماتية الحيوية والاحصاء الطبي معهد البحوث الطبية جامعة الإسكندرية
.....	د/ احسان اكرم احمد دغدي مدرس المعلوماتية الحيوية والاحصاء الطبي معهد البحوث الطبية جامعة الإسكندرية
.....	أ.م.د/ محمد هاني عاشور استاذ مساعد في قسم الجراحة معهد البحوث الطبية جامعة الإسكندرية